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Deliverable D6.2: Impact Assessment Report, mid-term version

D6.2

Impact Assessment Report, mid-term version.

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Executive Summary

This report tracks the impact coming from all the activities of the MaX team during the first 24 months of the project. It discloses the different groups on which the MaX activities have the potential to impact, and details the actual impacts achieved on each of them. We report on the outcomes of the technical Work Packages of MaX, and how these have been translated to the different target groups. We also describe the dissemination, communication, and stakeholders' engagement activities carried out to maximize those impacts.

A crucial goal of MaX is to make an impact in the community of users of quantum materials modelling codes, boosting their uptake, most importantly in the context of the most advanced and powerful HPC infrastructures available and to come. We present the results, in terms of impact, of actions taken in the technical work-packages of MaX towards this goal. Particularly important in this respect is the outcome of the efforts to deploy all the MaX codes in the principal EuroHPC machines currently available. The systematic benchmarking work has produced a series of data which are of great utility to the community of users to adopt these codes in the EuroHPC infrastructures.

A key part of the strategies to maximize the impact of the project lies in the Communication, Dissemination, and Training actions. The outcomes of these are described in detail in this deliverable. We analyze the achievements made in different communication channels (social media, webpage, newsletter, brochures), as well as the dissemination of results in publications, conferences and other events.

1. Introduction

The deliverable D6.2 *Impact Assessment Report, mid-term version* is the first report that tracks the impact of the overall MaX project. It presents the main target groups and the impacts expected on each of them. It also provides an update of the actions planned and those already taken during the first months of the project, to achieve these impacts. Finally, it also reports on the advance on the actions defined in the communication plan and their results so far.

This report starts by providing, in **Section 2**, an update on the overall strategy for achieving impact, in reference to that presented in the original workplan of the project.

A key step towards achieving impact is the identification of the groups and stakeholders on which the project results and outcomes can have an influence. **Section 3** gives an account of our present vision of the groups and communities which we consider potential stakeholders, expected impacts on each of them, and specific engagement strategies.

A crucial goal of MaX is to make an impact in the community of users of quantum materials modelling codes, boosting their uptake in the context of the most advanced and powerful HPC infrastructures available and to come. **Section 4** presents the results, in terms of impact, of actions taken in the technical work-packages of MaX towards this goal. Particularly important in this respect is the outcome of the efforts to deploy all the MaX codes in the principal EuroHPC machines currently available. The systematic benchmarking work has produced a series of data which are of great utility to the community of users to adopt these codes in the EuroHPC infrastructures. The adoption of scientific software engineering best practices is also described, as well as its impact on the community of developers of other codes outside of the MaX consortium. We also analyze in detail the impact produced on the community of code users in terms of the adoption of the MaX codes in academia and the industry, both in terms of publications and in the production of patents.

Section 5 explains the activities, outcomes and impact in the context of the European institutions and communities, with particular emphasis on those related to the HPC ecosystem.

In **Section 6** we give a detailed account of the communication and dissemination activities, including the MaX Website, Social Media Channels and Newsletter, the MaX 'Performance and Scalability' Brochure, the MaX training programs, the outcomes in the form of Scientific Publications and our participation in Stakeholders Engagement Events.

Finally, in **Section 7** we present the conclusions of this report. Additionally, **Section 9** contains annexes with detailed information on demographics of the MaX digital communities, the list of the scientific publications that have resulted from our work, and the third-party events attended by MaX members.

2. Strategy to Impact

MaX efforts are structured across two key domains: **Software for next-generation computing**, and **scientific grand challenges for global societal and industrial needs**. We outline below the strategic needs that motivate our efforts. We then detail the expected outcomes and the measures/actions for meeting the expected outcomes. At the end of the section, we describe the envisaged scientific, economic, and societal impacts beyond the project lifetime.

2.1. Strategic Needs

MaX is driven by critical technological and scientific imperatives that follow the evolution of high-performance computing and the pressing scientific grand challenges requiring advanced materials research. MaX effort is essential not only for advancing HPC-driven materials research but also for positioning Europe as a global leader in computational and materials science, sustainability, and high-performance computing applications. In the following, we describe MaX's strategic needs across its two key domains:

Software for next-generation computing

Developing highly optimized and scalable materials science software: The advent of exascale and post-exascale computing introduces unprecedented computational capabilities to the field of materials science. To fully leverage such resources, the development of highly optimized and scalable software is essential. Without such advancements in code capabilities, the potential of next-generation computing architectures will remain underutilized.

Leveraging exascale computing for the design and discovery of novel materials: Exascale computing is indispensable for achieving breakthrough capabilities in the design and discovery of novel materials. The complexity of materials simulations demands immense computational power to explore new physical and chemical properties, enabling innovations across multiple scientific and industrial sectors.

Consolidating a pan-European HPC ecosystem: MaX effort aims to consolidate and reinforce European leadership in computational materials science. Enhancing autonomy and sovereignty in this domain is crucial for maintaining competitiveness, reducing reliance on external technologies, and ensuring sustainable innovation within the European research and industrial ecosystem.

Minimizing energy consumption: Sustainability is also a major concern in HPC development. The energy demands of large-scale computing infrastructure necessitate a paradigm shift toward more energy-efficient applications. Developing computational tools that minimize power consumption

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without compromising performance is essential to ensuring the long-term viability of exascale computing.

Scientific grand challenges for global societal and industrial needs

Designing and discovering new materials: Progress in energy storage, climate change mitigation, advanced manufacturing, and healthcare, among other areas, relies on the ability to predict and engineer materials with tailored properties. The design and discovery of new materials are thus fundamental to addressing many of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the overarching Global Challenges outlined in Horizon Europe.

Tackling scientific grand challenges: achieving technological advancements involves tackling scientific grand challenges that surpass current computational capabilities. Exascale computing is a fundamental enabler in this context, providing the necessary power to model, simulate, and analyze materials at scales and complexities previously unattainable. By harnessing the upcoming computational performance, MaX contributes to solutions for technological innovation.

2.2. Expected outcomes

By the conclusion of the project, significant advancements are anticipated in both HPC software development and the application of exascale computing to address critical scientific challenges in the materials domain. The expected results are structured across the two key axes:

Software for next-generation computing

Delivery of advanced materials science codes optimized to leverage the full potential of pre-exascale and exascale computing infrastructures. MaX codes will be fully improved to ensure high performance and energy efficiency, and fully ported to be adaptable to the post-exascale era, ensuring their long-term applicability as computing architectures continue to evolve.

Design of a fully operational exascale workflow infrastructure. Rigorously tested, this infrastructure will streamline computational processes, facilitate integration across HPC platforms, and optimize resource utilization for large-scale simulations. Consequently, the implementation of exascale-oriented workflows for complex materials simulations will become standard practice, allowing

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researchers to tackle increasingly sophisticated problems with unprecedented accuracy and efficiency.

Deployment of MaX codes and workflows on EuroHPC machines. This will enhance accessibility of MaX codes for researchers and industry stakeholders, ensuring their practical application within the European supercomputing infrastructure.

Enhanced performance and energy efficiency of MaX codes and workflows to exploit the full potential of European exascale computing facilities. This optimization will maximize the return on investment in EuroHPC infrastructures, reinforcing European leadership in HPC-driven research.

Significant increase in the uptake of MaX codes across both academic and industrial sectors, leading to their widespread use in pre-exascale and exascale EuroHPC facilities. This broader adoption will expand the influence of the project's computational tools, fostering new scientific and technological developments.

Promotion of co-design activities with hardware manufacturers for the development of future computing architectures tailored to the needs of materials science simulations. This collaboration will ensure that upcoming HPC systems are optimized for scientific computing workloads.

Commercialization of HPC solutions, as European software vendors establish business collaborations with MaX research groups. This may lead to the development of commercial products based on MaX codes and workflows, fostering a robust European ecosystem for computational materials science software.

Scientific grand challenges for global societal and industrial needs

[Green Energy] Deeper understanding of excited states and non-adiabatic dynamics, which are fundamental to the efficient capturing of sunlight for electrical and chemical energy conversion. MaX will enable these insights in sustainable energy technologies.

[Information Technologies] Development of new computing paradigms based on the quantum behavior of materials. Additionally, advancements in the modeling of electronic and thermal transport in ICT devices will contribute to next-generation computing and communication technologies.

[Health] Employment of novel computational methodologies to predict mutations in SARS-CoV-2 variants that could potentially reduce antigen effectiveness. This will be achieved by modeling how mutations impact the strength of the antibody-antigen complex, contributing to more effective vaccine and therapeutic development.

2.3. Measures (Actions)

MaX incorporates a strategy to ensure the effective dissemination (D), exploitation (E), and communication (C) of the project results and reach the expected outcomes. Our approach is

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structured across the two key domains and integrates broad outreach initiatives across all project activities to maximize impact.

Software for next-generation computing

Code repositories and deployment publicly available (D&E) : To facilitate widespread adoption and usability, MaX codes and workflows will be made accessible to the academic and industrial communities through publicly available code repositories and deployment on the EuroHPC machines.

Benchmarking results publicly available (D&E): to demonstrate the performance and scalability of MaX codes in running efficiently on the EuroHPC machines. The results of these benchmarks will be disseminated through various communication channels, ensuring transparency and accessibility for the wider HPC community.

Scientific/technical advancements publicly disseminated (D): to contribute to scientific progress through the publication of technical advancements in high-impact scientific journals and conferences. These publications will focus on key developments such as performance optimization, parallel efficiency, new code capabilities, and the implementation of exascale workflows.

Strong digital presence (C): to ensure broad visibility of, and engagement with, the project outcomes. Updates on code developments, workflows, and scientific breakthroughs will be disseminated through MaX social media channels, MaX website, and MaX Newsletter to ensure accessibility to diverse audiences.

Open Access and Open Data compliance (D): to facilitate the adoption of codes and the sharing of documents, papers, and data among the research community and beyond. MaX will enforce Open Access and Open Data compliance, ensuring that all generated knowledge and data remain freely accessible, in alignment with best practices in open science.

Scientific grand challenges for global societal and industrial needs

Synergies with other EU and national projects (E): to fully integrate the scientific advancements generated when addressing scientific grand challenges. The knowledge and technologies emerging from such synergies will contribute to a broad range of research and innovation activities, fostering interdisciplinary applications, while ensuring continuous development and refinement of MaX tools in tackling societal challenges.

Dissemination of project outcomes through high-impact publications and conferences (E): to broaden the reach of MaX impact and explore potential paths for commercial exploitation of MaX tools and outcomes, particularly in the development of new products and technologies.

2.4. Wider scientific, economic, societal, and “human” impact of MaX

Scientific advances and new computational paradigms

- MaX will enable a novel approach to use computational science for materials research and innovation, unlocking unprecedented insights into the design and discovery of novel materials and devices. By enabling exascale-driven frontier research, the project will facilitate advances in materials simulations, which in turn will accelerate the development of next-generation technologies addressing pressing societal and global challenges.
- Benchmarking of MaX applications will facilitate the efficient utilization of EuroHPC exascale resources. This will ensure that researchers and industry users can fully exploit the capabilities of these infrastructures for materials simulations.
- The adoption of MaX solutions by developers of other codes and domains will accelerate the transition of various simulation tools to exascale environments, multiplying the impact of the project’s results across different computational fields.
- The development of new European processor technology will benefit from the co-design approach facilitated by MaX, particularly by incorporating advanced device solutions into future HPC architectures, ensuring that Europe remains at the forefront of cutting-edge computing technologies.

Economic impact

- MaX will contribute to maximizing the economic return on Europe's investment in HPC infrastructure. The increased demand for European exascale infrastructures demonstrates the critical need for these facilities in advanced computational research including computational materials science. By enabling materials discovery, MaX will facilitate technological advancements and innovation in multiple industries, including energy, IT, and health, which in turn drive economic and societal benefits.
- MaX is also expected to promote the growth of a European software industry in the materials domain, fostering the emergence of a competitive ecosystem of software vendors specialized in scientific computing. This will contribute to job creation, economic diversification, and European leadership in the field of HPC technologies.

“Human” impact (Impact within the broader community of computational & materials scientists)

- Thanks to MaX efforts, a larger community of researchers will be trained and specialized in the use of advanced computational simulations for materials science. This will contribute to the broader European Digital Agenda through the promotion of a highly skilled workforce proficient in HPC

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applications, which in turn will allow Europe to maintain its global competitiveness in computational science and technology.

From scientific grand challenges to global societal and industrial needs

- By optimizing exascale applications for materials simulations, MaX will promote a way to make HPC-driven research more energy-efficient while advancing materials science.
- MaX effort contributes to provide a blueprint for future scientific pursuits that rely on large-scale computational modeling. This will not only accelerate progress in materials discovery but also contribute to addressing broad global challenges aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Horizon Europe initiatives.
- Through the integration of MaX codes and exascale computing capabilities, the project will make previously inaccessible scientific challenges feasible. The ability to perform large-scale simulations of complex materials systems will open new frontiers in research, enabling discoveries in fields such as energy, information technology, and health.

3. MaX Target Groups for Impact

MaX goal is to cover the full exascale ecosystem by engaging both specialized and public audiences across Europe. MaX achievements will have a direct impact on several target groups, both during and beyond the project lifetime. For its third phase, MaX has identified seven target audiences on which the project envisages to impact thanks to its achievements.

1 The community of users of quantum materials modelling codes

This is the core target group of MaX. This community is broadly composed of **researchers and scientists** working in the fields of materials science, chemistry, catalysis, condensed matter physics, fluids, geophysics, nanoscience, biomolecular engineering, and many other fields where the study of the behavior of condensed matter systems at the atomic level is relevant.

A community of growing importance is that of **users/developers of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning** for materials discovery, who are users of the data that our electronic structure codes can provide for the training of their models.

IMPACT 1 Up-take by an increased number of researchers (both from industry and academia), who adopt the MaX codes within their toolbox for R&D&I activities.

2 Supercomputers and HPC Competence Centres

This target group involves the computational platforms where the MaX codes and workflows are being deployed and run. The community of Supercomputers and HPC Competence Centres

aims to provide exascale-class capabilities to academic and industry professionals, hence they are interested in advancements in computational power, energy efficiency, and scalability of codes.

IMPACT 2 Maximise the overall demand, use and best exploitation of the EuroHPC infrastructures.

3 Code developers of other quantum materials modeling codes

This target group involves application code developers dealing with quantum materials modelling. This community is interested in evolving and adapting their codes to the new exascale environments, hence they might be interested in the methodological advances, algorithms, libraries, middleware, etc. provided by MaX and made available in open source form through MaX codes' repositories and documentations.

IMPACT 3 Maximise the efficiency of the transfer of results through separation of concerns, modularisation, and encapsulation of MaX development environments and data.

4 Hardware (HW) manufacturers

This target group involves industrial actors. This community is interested in integrating the needs of high-level software design in the HPC technology. Relevant companies working on the development of HPC technologies towards exascale participate in the consortium and benefit from the feedback provided during the co-design activities conducted in conjunction with MaX software developers.

IMPACT 4 Outputs resulting from the co-design activities. Mutual adaptation of the HW characteristics to the optimal needs of MaX codes. Access of MaX codes to advanced HW. Minimization of the energy footprint of the execution of MaX codes on EuroHPC infrastructures.

5 Independent Software Vendors (ISV)

This target group is a crucial potential actor for the exploitation of MaX results. This community might be interested in including MaX open-source codes into the services they provide to their

clients. Through ISV, MaX software solutions could be incorporated into commercial services and products.

IMPACT 5 Opening of new business opportunities. Primary economic impact in terms of jobs and wealth creation. Possible exploitation channel for MaX software developments (restricted to companies within the European Union and the Participating States of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking).

6 Policy makers and society at large

This community supports the return on investment in exascale facilities and software. MaX aims to create a positive perception of the European efforts in developing and exploiting the next generation of computers and codes. European citizens are interested in engaging with outreach events and contents to learn more about the discoveries made in the fields of materials and computer sciences. In addition, thanks to specific educational content, young talents can feel inspired to pursue computing-related disciplines and careers.

IMPACT 6 Return on investment. Knowledge building. Raise public awareness about materials science and HPC. Inspire new talent in materials/computing fields.

7 Industry

Moving towards EU industrial leadership in advanced materials is a priority for the EU, and computational materials design and discovery is a key component of the EU strategy. The MaX codes are a crucial link in the growing ecosystem encompassing HPC facilities, data infrastructures, AI factories, etc. MaX solutions (codes and workflows) should enhance the capabilities of the industry to become more competitive, not only in the area of advanced materials, but also in others like pharma, chemical processes and products, clean energy, quantum technologies and many others.

IMPACT 7 Boost industrial competitiveness through the tools (codes and workflows) developed in MaX, through accelerated design and discovery of materials and other high added value products.

The first six groups were already identified and analyzed in our original proposal, as reflected in the Grant Agreement. The last one, Industry, has been added after the commencement of the project. Although Industry was already identified and mentioned as part of some of the other target groups (for example, within the community of users of our codes, HW vendors, ISVs, etc), we have decided to highlight the importance that MaX gives to the industrial up-take and impact by explicitly including

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it among our target groups. Part of the analysis we make below contains indicators of this impact, like the numbers of patents filed in the industry that make use of our simulation codes.

MaX has designed and implemented tailored strategies/approaches to enhance the project's impact across the exascale ecosystem and effectively reach the project's different target audiences. In the next sections, we detail the impact resulting from the different actions undertaken by MaX.

4. Impact of the MaX Codes and Workflows

4.1. Deployment of MaX lighthouse codes on EuroHPC infrastructures

The first two years of MaX have largely overlapped with the installation and start-up of the EuroHPC machines across Europe. The work on the MaX codes in previous MaX editions has positioned us in an optimal situation to install, deploy, test, and benchmark them in these HPC infrastructures. This has come with a very large amount of work and effort during this reporting period, given the diversity of architectures but also the need to apply for access on an individual basis for each specific machine and each single code. Nevertheless, the outcome of our work has been outstanding, resulting in all the MaX codes being already supported, demonstrated, deployed or benchmarked on all the major EuroHPC machines and their different partitions.

In Table 4.1.1 we present an update of the situation of the five MaX codes (Quantum ESPRESSO, YAMBO, SIESTA, BigDFT, and FLEUR) in the different EuroHPC infrastructures. The state of each code on each machine/partition is marked with a letter, according to the following nomenclature:

- W: Work in Progress
- S: Supported Architecture (tested on similar architectures)
- D: Demonstrated (developers installation)
- M: Deployed (module available)
- B: Benchmark available

As shown in the table, there is a large number of deployments already done (codes for which a module has been deployed in a particular machine/partition). In many other cases, we have demonstrated the execution of the codes on specific machines/partitions through an installation by the developers, although modules have not yet been deployed. For all the cases for which this developers' installation has not yet been possible (due to any reason, such as lack of access to the machine), we have at least tested the execution of the codes on similar architectures, which gives strong confidence on the feasibility of the deployment soon. Only for two cases (SIESTA in DEUCALION and FLEUR in the LUMI-G partition) we have not reached this point yet. We note that the situation is different for each code, with the ones that have a larger user's base being more advanced in their deployment.

It is also to be noted that a large effort has been made in producing a set of benchmarks of each code on different machines (also reported in the Table). We expect that these benchmarks, which were published on October 25 2024 and are available on the MaX website, will have a large impact on the community of users, as they will provide specific scaling and performance information in each machine, allowing them to prepare their proposals for access to HPC proposals and to plan their executions efficiently.

The advances on the deployment and benchmarking of our codes in the EuroHPC facilities is contributing to Impacts 1 (Up-take of the MaX codes by an increased number of researchers) and Impact 2 (Maximise the overall demand and use of the EuroHPC infrastructures). Fully achieving these impacts will occur progressively during and after second half of the MaX project, as we complete the offer of codes deployed in the EuroHPC machines and partitions, the results of our deployment are

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spread throughout the community, our modules adopted and announced by the HPC centres, and our benchmarks used by the researchers to prepare their applications and plan their executions.

EuroHPC Machines and Partitions	Architecture Type		Quantum ESPRESSO	YAMBO	SIESTA	BigDFT	FLEUR	
	CPU	GPU						
DEUCALION	ARM	A64FX (ARM)	D	D	W	S	S	
	CPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	S	S	D+B	S	S	
	GPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	NVIDIA A100	S	S	D+B	S	S
DISCOVERER	CPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	M	S	D+B	S	S	
KAROLINA	CPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	M	M	D+B	D	D	
	GPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	NVIDIA A100	M	M	D+B	S	S
JUPITER	Cluster	SiPearl Rhea1 (ARM)						
	Booster	NVIDIA GH200 (ARM+H100)					D	
LEONARDO	DCGP	INTEL SapphireRapids (x86)	M+B	M+B	M+B	M	M	
	Booster	INTEL IceLake (x86)	NVIDIA A100+	M+B	M+B	M+B	M+B	M+B
LUMI	LUMI-C	AMD EPYC (x86)	M+B	M	D+B	S	S	
	LUMI-G	AMD EPYC (x86)	AMD MI250X	M+B	D+B	D	D	W
MareNostrum5	GPP	INTEL SapphireRapids (x86)	M+B	D+B	M+B	D	D	
	ACC	INTEL SapphireRapids (x86)	NVIDIA H100	M+B	D+B	M+B	S	D
	NGT GPP	NVIDIA Grace (ARM)						
MELUXINA	CPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	D	D	D+B	S	S	
	GPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	NVIDIA A100	M	M	D+B	S	S
VEGA	CPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	M	M	D+B	S	S	
	GPU	AMD EPYC (x86)	NVIDIA A100	M	M	D(5)+B, M(4)	M	S

Table 4.1.1: Current situation for the deployment of the different MaX codes in the EuroHPC machines. Legend (see also main text): W Work in Progress; S Supported Architecture (tested on similar architectures); D Demonstrated (developers installation); M Deployed; B Benchmark available.

4.2. Software Engineering and the Technical impact of MaX codes

Software Engineering Best Practices

One of the most important outcomes of the present and two previous MaX projects has been the adoption of Scientific Software (SW) engineering best practices in the design, development, maintenance, and documentation of the MaX codes. The following table provides a detailed account on the advances made on each individual code, including issues such as Continuous Integration (CI), personnel, code development organization and management, and others.

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MaX code	Adopted Scientific SW engineering best practices
Quantum ESPRESSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New developments (technical or about physics) happen in branches, mostly from developers' forks. Upon review, they are merged into the "develop" branch of the main git repository via merge (pull) requests. • At least one expert developer must approve merge requests. • CI: all pushed commits, and merge requests are tested versus two different compilations using autoconf and cmake. Basic unit testing is run with the GCC toolchain and CMake. • CI: A full regression test is executed nightly, triggered by changes to the "develop" branch. The regression test uses an extensive test suite executed on x86_64 hardware with different compilers (GCC, Intel, NVHPC-SDK), compilation options (debug, HDF5), and parallel environments (OpenMP, MPI, GPU). • The "master" branch is used for stable releases.
YAMBO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A professional Scientific SW engineer is full-time dedicated to the Yambo project. • CI: all major commits and all merge requests need to comply (no errors) with runs of the Yambo test-suite done under diverse HPC environments (HPC architectures, serial, MPI parallel up to 16 cores and multiple data distribution schemes, MPI+OpenMP, MPI+CUDA). • A dedicated and customized structure of branches is provided in the main git repository to deal with the needs of the development team (master, tech-master, maintain-master, phys-master). • Scientific projects are developed in dedicated branches (both public and private, depending on the needs), and included in the main repo via pull requests. • Each pull request must satisfy regression tests and is discussed at least once by a team of senior developers.
SIESTA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development is fully integrated in the Gitlab platform, with 'dev' and 'rel-X.Y' branches (for bleeding-edge development and releases, respectively) and contributed feature branches that are merged into the "dev" branch after approval of formal merge requests. • Gitlab development is organized via milestones, to which issues and merge requests are assigned following discussion among core developers. • A curating team of code maintainers meets several times a month to discuss the direction of development and review current milestones. • The building process is based on CMake, automatically integrating a suite of independent libraries originating in the Siesta project and external libraries. • Spack recipes are provided for deployment in HPC centres. Easybuild recipes are on the way. • CI in place for building and updating documentation. It is being extended for automatic deployment on EuroHPC machines.
BigDFT	<p>The software engineering practices adopted for BigDFT emphasize modularity, maintainability, and flexibility, aligning with the principles of modern software development. Here are the main practices implemented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Package Modularity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Codebase split into distinct modular packages, enabling independent development, testing and deployment. ◦ Packages are categorized as native (internally developed) and upstream (external dependencies), clearly delineating ownership and functionality. • Flexible Build System: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ A modular build system based on the <i>Jhbuild</i> project allows tailored compilation of individual packages. ◦ This approach ensures minimal side-effects between components and accommodates system-specific requirements, especially on large supercomputers. • Code Reusability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Key libraries like <i>futile</i>, <i>psolver</i>, and <i>CheSS</i> are designed for use both within BigDFT and independently, promoting reusability across other projects. • Standards in I/O and Interoperability:

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Yaml is extensively used for input and output, supported by libraries like libyaml and PyYaml, ensuring consistency and compatibility with external tools. • Separation of Concerns: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Each package handles specific responsibilities, from low-level operations (futile) to domain-specific tasks (e.g., electronic structure calculations with bigdft-core). • Versioning and Dependency Management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Optional and upstream packages can be selectively included, simplifying installation in environments with varying dependencies.
FLEUR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development is documented and supported by self-hosted Gitlab instances. • Adaptive development model in which larger changes are performed in dedicated branches. • CI testing for each commit and more extensive overnight tests using multiple compilers. • Continuous benchmarking to identify newly introduced performance degradation. • Code coverage monitoring of the test suite. • Build system based on CMake, inclusion of external dependencies into build process when possible. • Recipe for the spack package-manager. • Regular (bi-weekly) meeting of developers to discuss progress, changes and plans.

These advances have been possible largely by the sharing of knowledge among the MaX partners. The MaX community (including the groups developing the MaX codes, but also other partners like the HPC centres) encloses a growing number of professional software engineers who have driven the incorporation of these best practices into the MaX codes. These teams have established interactions and collaborations with many SW development experts in different institutions, both within and outside of MaX. The next table provides a report of such interactions.

MaX code	Collaborations with SW engineering experts
Quantum ESPRESSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with NVIDIA SW engineers (Piero Altoé, Louis Stuber, M. Fatica + others): GPU porting NV architectures using OpenACC. • Collaboration with AMD SW engineers (Ossian O'Reilly, Jacob Kurzac, Quentarius Moore, Alfio Lazzaro, Pierre Carrere): GPU porting on AMD/LUMI arch, using OpenMP5. • Collaboration with INTEL SW engineers (G. Rossi in particular): GPU porting on INTEL arch, using OpenMP5. • Interaction with CINECA HPC experts (F. Affinito, L. Bellentani, S. Orlandini). • Testing and evaluating computational libraries for GPUs, such as accelerated and/or distributed eigensolvers and mixed-precision DGEMMs for NVidia GPUs, alternative communications libraries (NCCL).
YAMBO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with NVIDIA SW engineers (GPU porting NV architectures using CUDA-F). • Collaboration with AMD SW engineers (GPU porting on AMD/LUMI arch, using OpenMP-GPU). • Collaboration with INTEL SW engineers (e.g., G. Rossi, for development of DeviceXlib and GPU porting on INTEL arch, using OpenMP-GPU). • Interaction with CINECA HPC experts (F. Affinito, L. Bellentani, S. Orlandini, M. Montagna). • Interaction with IT4I HPC experts (L. Riha, F. Vaverka). • Interaction with BSC HPC experts (J. Gutierrez, R. Grima). • Interaction, within the MaX consortium with ARM (MaX-2), EVIDEN, SiPEARL (MaX-3). • Interaction with SLEPC developers (LinAlg). • Interaction with ChASE developers (linAlg).
SIESTA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with BSC experts (Rogeli Grima, Julio Gutiérrez) on code development and benchmarks.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with CINECA experts (Laura Bellentani, Mariella Ipolito) on profiling. • Collaboration with experts in IJS (Jan Jona Javorsek, Alja Prah) on CI/CD. • Collaboration with IT4I expert (Ada Böhm) on HyperQueue integration.
BigDFT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical Contributions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ OpenCL Porting: B. Videau, from the Laboratoire d'Informatique de Grenoble (LIG), started the OpenCL implementation, enabling support for a wide range of GPU architectures. ◦ CUDA Porting: A. Degomme, while at the Laboratoire d'Informatique de Grenoble and later at Basel University, developed the CUDA implementation, optimizing BigDFT for NVIDIA GPUs. ◦ SYCL Porting: C. Bauinger of Intel Corporation extended BigDFT's capabilities to SYCL platforms, ensuring compatibility with Intel GPUs and other SYCL-compliant hardware. • Current and Upcoming Collaborations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ EPICURE Program: A collaboration with the CINES centre in Montpellier is about to begin, focusing on optimizing the Poisson solver for heterogeneous GPU architectures. ◦ CExA Initiative: As part of the CExA project, BigDFT will integrate the Kokkos portability framework, further improving scalability and adaptability for exascale supercomputing platforms.
FLEUR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration within the MaX WPs. • Regular participation in hackathons and dedicated coding, software tuning and performance assessment workshops (e.g. aiXcelerate). • Exchange with SW experts from JSC.

As a result of all these activities and efforts, MaX codes have made the following technical impacts outside the MaX consortium:

MaX code	Technical impact outside the consortium
Quantum ESPRESSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QE is used as a benchmark for HPC procurements. • The DARE consortium has selected QE as one of the strategic applications to port and benchmark along the development of the RISC-V European HPC technology. • QE is used as a development platform. • QE is used as a quantum engine (ASE, QEpy, ...).
YAMBO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yambo used as development platform by third party users: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ C. Morice (Uni Paris Saclay) qsGW. ◦ M. Nalobothula (Uni Luxembourg), symmetry analysis of excitonic states; adv schemes for BSE diagonalization; data management for el-ph and exc-ph coupling. ◦ Chase team (Jülich Supercomputing Centre) integration of Chase linear algebra library ◦ SlepC Team (Universitat Politecnica de Valencia) integration of SlepC library • Yambo is a provider of plugins and workflows for the AiiDA platform. • Yambo is among the main codes in other projects as EuroHPC project Hanami, MSCA network (Times), Italian National Centre on HPC, Big Data and Quantum Computing
SIESTA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIMUNE Atomistics, a start-up company in San Sebastián (Spain) develops software for industrial users that uses SIESTA as a quantum engine for complex materials workflows. • The JSOL Corporation (a large company based in Japan) has incorporated SIESTA as its quantum engine in their JOCTA, its integrated system for multiscale modeling and simulations in materials, within their JSOL Computer Aided Engineering toolset. JOCTA users can execute SIESTA from the JOCTA platform seamlessly with other simulation tools at larger size and time scales. • SIESTA is used as a calculator in ASE (Atomic Simulation Environment) and PySCF • SIESTA is a provider of plugins and workflows for the AiiDA platform.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIESTA has an impact on the Wannier90 community as it provides an interface for postprocessing, but also incorporates Wannier90 as a library for its internal use in SIESTA calculations. • SIESTA is the basis for several third-party academic codes, which use its output as the starting point of their calculations. Examples are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ BerkeleyGW, a GW and Bethe-Salpeter code for excited states by Steven G. Louie (UC-Berkeley) ◦ FIESTA – a gaussian-based GW code developed by Xavier Blasé (CNRS). ◦ TDEP – a code for vibrational and thermal properties of materials by Olle Hellman (Weizmann Institute) ◦ USPEX, a crystallographic simulation code under BSD licence, by Artem Oganov (Slotech, Russia) ◦ DJmol, a platform for molecular modeling ◦ CIF2WAN, a code which links SIESTA with Wannier90
BigDFT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wavelet-Based Formalism: BigDFT introduced a novel wavelet-based formalism, providing systematic and adaptive precision. This makes it uniquely suited for large-scale systems, offering an edge over traditional plane-wave or localized-basis methods in terms of accuracy and flexibility. • GPU Enablement and Portability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ BigDFT was one of the first GPU-accelerated DFT codes, enabling researchers to fully exploit the computational power of GPUs. ◦ Its inclusion in NVIDIA's NVC Container registry underscored its portability and readiness for GPU platforms, influencing how other codes approached GPU optimization. • Scalability: With highly scalable implementations, BigDFT has been used on some of the world's fastest supercomputers in the last decade. Its ability to handle large systems efficiently has made it a go-to choice for high-throughput studies in material science and biology. • Community Influence BigDFT's methodologies, such as its linear-scaling algorithms and Poisson solver innovations, have influenced subsequent developments in electronic structure theory and parallel programming frameworks.
FLEUR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The development team is part of the HiRSE collaboration of the Helmholtz-Association on Research Software Engineering. • AiiDA-FLEUR plugin available, including a comprehensive set of workflows for HTC. • Impact into the Wannier90 community by interfacing and providing property calculators. • Feedback to HPC providers, compiler and other external software developers regarding issues, bugs and limitations encountered.

Adoption of MaX modules and libraries by other codes

MaX has made a great effort towards modularization and interoperability of codes, to achieve several goals. One of them is to maximize the reuse of our software in other codes. This is greatly facilitated by the development of libraries, which perform well defined tasks, and can be utilized in other codes. Also, by the construction of modules, which can be linked to build software on top of the MaX codes. The impact of all this work has crystallized in the integration of the MaX modules and libraries in materials modelling software developed by the broader community. The following table summarizes the most relevant cases.

MaX code	Incorporation of MaX Modules and Libraries to other software
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Quantum ESPRESSO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WEST (https://west-code.org), • GiPAW (https://github.com/dceresoli/qe-gipaw), • SternheimerGW (https://github.com/QEF/SternheimerGW) • EPW (distributed and released along with QE https://epw-code.org/), • QePy (http://qepy.rutgers.edu/), • ENVIRON (http://www.quantum-environ.org/team.html, reuses FFTXlib) • d3q + thermal2 (https://anharmonic.github.io/) • Thermo_pw (https://dalcorsogithub.io/thermo_pw/) • Koopmans (https://koopmans-functionals.org/en/latest/)
YAMBO	<p>Development of deviceXlib as a general-purpose but domain specific performance portability layer. It is developed within MaX, and used in Yambo and QE (the latter interfacing with an old version of the lib)</p> <p>This library is publicly available: https://gitlab.com/max-centre/components/devicexlib</p>
SIESTA	<p>The following libraries, developed from SIESTA, are used by the following codes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • xmlf90: a suite of libraries to handle XML in Fortran. Used by DFTB+ and Abinit • Libpsml: a library to handle pseudopotentials in PSML format. Used by Abinit • LibOMM: a library to solve the Kohn-Sham equation as a generalized eigenvalue problem using the orbital minimization method. It is part of ELSI, and can be used by the codes which have an interface with ELSI (DFTB+, FHI-Aims). • libgridxc: a library for the computation of exchange and correlation energies and potentials in radial and 3D grids. It is being considered for its incorporation in BigDFT (pero no usada aún) • libfdf: a library that implements FDF (Flexible Data Format, designed within the Siesta project to simplify the handling of input options). Not used explicitly in any code, to our knowledge, but has inspired several input formats and handling of several codes.
BigDFT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psolver: a Poisson solver developed within the BigDFT project. Used by Octopus, Abinit and Conquest (undistributed prior to the open source version), and it is currently being installed in SIESTA. • PyBigDFT: a collection of Python Modules that are conceived for pre- and post- processing of BigDFT input and output files. Used by NTchem • bundler: a package for developing a common infrastructure for compiling and linking together libraries for electronic structure codes. It is employed as the basis for the ESL bundle. • RemoteManager: the submission engine developed from the internal job submission system used within PyBigDFT. It is used by NTchem.

Co-design: Enabling energy efficiency of the MaX codes in EuroHPC machine

Besides the deployment of MaX codes in the EuroHPC infrastructure, a large amount of work has been devoted to the study of runtime execution parameters on the energy efficiency of the simulation runs in those machines. Deliverable D4.2 presented the results of this work as reached by month 18 of the present MaX project. They are a first indication to HPC system administrators and code users of ways to reduce the energy consumption without a significant effort. Table 4.2.1 exemplifies the studies performed and results obtained for a particular set of hardware platforms based on the AMD Zen2 and Zen3 CPU architectures and Nvidia A100 GPU architecture, which are a significant portion of the EuroHPC systems. In particular, these results show how we can save energy using static tuning, which means that we set a CPU frequency(ies) before application execution. Significant reductions in the energy usage of up can be achieved without a noticeable degradation of the execution time (data shown in the 1st row of Table Energy), while more ambitious energy savings (up to 26%) are possible with an acceptable increase of runtime (data shown in the 2nd row of Table Energy). More ambitious dynamic modification of the hardware configuration may bring higher energy savings without impacting application performance. These and upcoming results will guide the HPC centres and code users to adapt their execution parameters to reduce the energy footprint of the MaX codes.

	Quantum ESPRESSO	YAMBO	SIESTA	BigDFT	FLEUR
	Energy consumption reduction[kJ] / Runtime[s]				
	1st row - results with no runtime extension (runtime close to 100% of default)				
	2nd row - results for maximum energy savings				
AMD Zen2	-2% / 100% -8% / 112%	-6% / 100% -23% / 115%	-15% / 100% -24% / 102%	-17% / 101% -26% / 115%	-3% / 101% -9% / 107%
AMD Zen3	-8% / 100% -12% / 110%	-19% / 100% -22% / 109%	-15% / 101% -24% / 107%	-12% / 102% -23% / 113%	-7% / 101% -13% / 112%
Nvidia A100	-7% / 101% -10% / 111%	0% / 100% -7% / 111%	-7% / 101% -9% / 102%	-6% / 102% -9% / 109%	-6% / 101% -8% / 104%

Table 4.2.1: Example of energy consumption reduction for the MaX flagship codes using static tuning in several types of processors, presented in Deliverable D4.2.

4.3. Workflows: the AiiDA registry

While individual codes and libraries (together with the underlying system software stack) are the low-level tools for the use of computational resources, workflows constitute the top-level layer. Currently, the simulations of materials aim to tackle properties of an increasing degree of complexity, which are not the result of a single calculation and often require several levels of physical description. Computing some properties often requires performing many calculations of a given physical quantity, each of which entails a single run of a given simulation code. In other occasions, the output of a given code serves as input to another one that accounts for a different level of the physical description. In most

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cases, the interactions between these many calculations and physical levels involves a feedback loop, which requires a high level of management in defining the tasks within each process. Automating, orchestrating and dispatching all these processes in a HPC environment is the role of the Workflows.

MaX has a strong focus on the development of workflows for exascale environments for materials R+D+I. This effort has been focused both on constructing software tools to handle complex workflows in exascale infrastructures, and to use these tools to build specific workflows for concrete applications in materials research. Deliverable 2.1 “Exascale workflow design”, submitted at month 12 of the current MaX project, summarized the advances made during the first year of the project.

While the major impact of this infrastructure of workflows in enabling scientific advancements and industrial transfer will show up in the future, here we hint on the growth of the development of plugins and workflow packages by the community, based on the AiiDA infrastructure (one of the main workflow tools developed within MaX). The list of plugins in the AiiDA registry¹ (summarized in Table 4.3.1) shows an average increase of nearly 50%. Remarkably, the number of workflows (the main focus of MaX), has grown by 76% during the current MaX project.

	Plugins MaX2 (9/2022)	Packages MaX2 (9/2022)	Plugins (M25, 01/2025)	Packages (M25, 01/2025)	Plugins % growth	Packages % growth
Calculations	127	53	170	70	34%	32%
Parsers	108	54	149	71	38%	31%
Data	92	27	132	41	43%	52%
Workflows	125	36	220	50	76%	39%
Others	99	29	147	52	48%	79%

Table 4.3.1. The AiiDa registry values at the end of the former MaX Project (9/2022), and at M25 of the current MaX (01/2025), with growth percentages.

4.4. Materials Cloud: a platform for data in computational materials science

Data is expected to be one of the cornerstones of the future research and discovery of materials. The MaX community (including the large cohort of MaX code users) is continuously contributing data resulting from calculations enabled by its flagship codes. One key instrument in this endeavor is the [Materials Cloud](#)², a platform dedicated to sharing resources for computational materials science,

¹ <https://aiida-team.github.io/aiida-registry/>

² Talirz, L., Kumbhar, S., Passaro, E. *et al.* Materials Cloud, a platform for open computational science. *Sci Data* **7**, 299 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-00637-5>, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-020-00637-5>

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providing services for archiving and disseminating both raw and curated data, alongside data analytics tools and educational resources.

Established as an important part of the MaX efforts during its previous phases, in collaboration with the Marvel Swiss Centre and with support from other European initiatives, the platform has consistently made significant efforts in expanding its offerings and enhancing user experience. Importantly, Materials Cloud is now available as a federated data repository, already available on different HPC centres (so far Cineca and FZJ Juelich, in addition to CSCS).

The platform receives nearly [20,000 visits](#) per month from various countries (see details in Figure 4.4.1), including several European nations as well as China, the U.S., India, Japan. Presently it hosts more than 30 million crystal structures, within which more than 13 million with associated DFT SCF calculations, which are available for download from the Archive section.

Figure 4.4.1: Number of unique page visits to Materials Cloud per month (left) and per country (right), as on Oct 25, 2024.

Some of the recent updates of the Materials Cloud include the [Quantum ESPRESSO input generator](#) tool with improved k-point sampling/smearing protocols, as well as the addition of new examples to the [interactive phonon visualizer](#) featuring common 3D crystals. A new [cell2mol](#) tool has been introduced to help users interpret crystallographic data and retrieve various properties of molecular complexes and their components.

Some of the Discover sections have also been updated. In particular, following the release of the version 1.3.0 of the Standard Solid-State Pseudopotentials (SSSP) in 2023, the [Materials Cloud 3D](#) (MC3D) crystals database has been updated and the web interface has been redesigned. MC3D now features more than 33,000 materials in the PBEsol-v1 dataset, calculated using the PBEsol DFT functional, supplementing the prior PBE-v1 dataset. MC3D has a new and improved web interface and contains 33674 materials in the PBEsol dataset (in addition to the previous PBE-v1 dataset).

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Additionally, powder X-ray diffraction analysis is available for all structures. A screenshot of the web interface of MC3D is shown in Figure 4.4.2.

On April 3, 2024, the [Materials Cloud Archive](#) repository celebrated reaching the milestone of 1,000 publications. Furthermore, an automated service has been established to launch the [OPTIMADE APIs](#) directly from Archive entries.

Figure 4.4.2: Web interface for the Materials Cloud 3D Crystal Database.

4.5. Uptake of MaX codes and workflows by academic and industrial users

MaX codes are very widespread, and are widely used for academic and industrial communities for their R+D+I activities.

Journal citations to MaX codes

A direct measure of the evolution of the usage of MaX codes in academic research is given by the citation to the papers describing the MaX codes in publications that appear each year in the scientific literature. Figure 4.5.1 shows the cumulative number of citations for the five MaX flagship codes. The total number of citations adds up to an impressive figure above 40,000, showing a steady and sustained growth. While most citations correspond to Quantum ESPRESSO and SIESTA (those being the two codes with a more general purpose and range of applications), the other (more niche-application) codes also show a significant increase in the last few years. These numbers demonstrate that the MaX codes are universal research tools, with a larger impact than many large-scale experimental facilities, and which enable a tremendous amount of research to be developed

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worldwide. As a reference, the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble (France), one of the largest experimental scientific facilities in Europe, has produced 37,000 publications since its inauguration in 1994 (see [link](#)).

Figure 4.5.1: Cumulative Number of citations to the MaX Lighthouse codes' reference papers, per year and per code. Data was obtained from the Web of Science.

Geographical distribution of MaX codes based on journal citations

Again, based on the citations to the MaX codes references in the academic literature, the users of the MaX codes are very much spread around the globe, with large communities in the European Union, the US and Asia (mainly in China, India, but also in Japan and several countries in the Middle East), and smaller but substantial numbers in the rest of America, Africa and Oceania, as shown in Figure 4.5.2. Within Europe, the usage is very much widespread, with the largest communities in Germany, Italy, France, Spain, and the UK.

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Figure 4.5.2: Distribution of users of the MaX Flagship codes in 2024, in the world (top) and in Europe, except Russia (bottom). Data correspond to authors' affiliations in peer-reviewed publications citing the MaX codes. The size of the largest bubble corresponds to 1000 publications in the top panel and 300 in the bottom panel, respectively. Source: Web of Science. Created with Datawrapper.

Industrial impact of the usage of MaX codes

An important measure of the impact of the codes on the productive sector is their uptake by companies and industries. This is not straightforward to measure, as the majority of the use in the industrial environment is confidential and not publicly disclosed. However, we have found that there are two indicators to gauge this impact, based on public data.

The first one comes, again, from the affiliations in the scientific publications that reference any of the MaX codes. We have selected those affiliations which correspond to companies, in any industrial sector of activity. We have found a total of 225 such entries, which are an impressive measure of the

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widespread usage of the MaX codes in the ecosystem of companies and industrial users. The comprehensive list of companies is included in Appendix 1.

The second indicator is related to the production of patents. In this case, we have restricted our search to the two codes with the widest users' base: Quantum ESPRESSO and SIESTA. We have searched in Espacenet (<https://worldwide.espacenet.com>), the official search engine of the European Patent Office (EPO), for entries containing the keywords "SIESTA", "Quantum ESPRESSO" or "pwscf". In the case of SIESTA, we had to refine our search including the keywords "DFT" or "simulation". After discarding a few patents that matched the search criteria but unrelated to the two MaX codes, we found a total of 70 patents that quote the SIESTA code, and 269 patents that quote Quantum ESPRESSO. Among the institutions filing the patents, there are important companies such as Bosch, Braun, Toyota, Hitachi, AMD, Mitsubishi, Fujitsu, Synopsys, Xiaomi. We find that not all these companies are in the list of affiliations in publications citing the MaX codes, indicating the fact that much of the work with our codes in the industrial environment is not published in academic journals, and that the usage in the industry is more widespread than what the academic publications (which is already very significant) may seem to indicate.

It is interesting to make an analysis of the themes in which the patents using MaX codes were filed. Figure 4.5.3 shows the International Patent Classification codes of the patents that mention Quantum ESPRESSO. A large portion of the patents (almost one third) are related to chemistry and metallurgy, which traditionally has been a field in which atomistic simulations have been relevant. Notably, MaX codes are now contributing to this area where quantum chemistry codes traditionally dominate the markets. The areas of "Physics" and "Electricity" together, enclosing electric elements, information and communication technologies, computing and measuring, take half of the patents. This demonstrates the usefulness of the MaX codes in addressing industrial topics closely related to two of our scientific grand challenges for global societal and industrial needs: Green Energy and ICT. The connection with our third social challenge (Health) is not visible in these results, which is likely because biologically relevant systems and processes are not the best case for Quantum ESPRESSO, as they require large systems sizes and simulation times, more accessible to other codes like BigDFT and SIESTA. In any case, although this analysis is quite restricted to a particular code, it gives an overall idea of the actual impact of our codes for industrial development.

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Figure 4.5.3. International Patent Classification codes of the patents mentioning Quantum ESPRESSO, aggregated in Sections (internal chart) and Classes (external chart). Only Classes containing more than 2.5% of the documents have been reported. The grey Sections refer to A - HUMAN NECESSITIES (1.4%) and F - MECHANICAL ENGINEERING (1.4%). Source: Espacenet, European Patent Office.

Impact on Independent Software Vendors

Although MaX codes are all free and open-source software, they can still contribute to the creation of economic value for Independent Software Vendors (ISVs). These for-profit companies build added value products around the MaX codes, by providing graphical user interfaces (GUIs), plugins and interfaces to proprietary simulation software, specialized workflows, and connections to AI/ML and other data-based resources.

Some of these ISV companies were created in the environment of (or have commercial agreements with) the communities of the developers of the MaX codes, while others are unrelated to our groups. Examples of both are provided below:

SIMUNE Atomistics S.L. (<https://www.simuneatomistics.com>) is a start-up company created in 2014 in San Sebastián (Spain), by the CICNanoGUNE research centre, and some of the main developers of SIESTA. SIMUNE provides software tools, utilities and services for materials research. SIMUNE commercializes software like ASAP (Atomistic Simulation Advanced Platform), a platform for materials modelling using *ab-initio* methods, which offers powerful GUIs to some of which use MaX codes (SIESTA and Quantum ESPRESSO), together with workflows to automatize processes involved in the calculation of complex physical properties. SIMUNE has recently signed contracts with three ISVs: the

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JSOL Corporation, Kostech, and DHIO Research, for the commercial distribution of ASAP in Japan, Korea and India, respectively.

JSOL Corporation (<https://www.jsol-cae.com/en/>) incorporates SIESTA as the quantum engine of one of its products: JOCTA (<https://www.j-octa.com/>), an integrated system for multiscale modeling and simulation of materials. The interface between JOCTA and SIESTA was built in collaboration with SIMUNE, which obtains royalties for every licence of the interface sold by JSOL to its customers.

Materys (<https://www.materys.com>) is a startup company created in 2023 with the participation of S. Baroni (PI of MaX at SISSA), to advance materials innovation through computational science. Materys harnesses high-throughput DFT and machine learning to accelerate materials discovery. The Materys platform offers a 3D interactive molecular builder, automation of complex simulations, data management and visualization of simulation results in a dashboard offering a seamless experience. The computational workflows offered will be deployed as SaaS, allowing the functionality of Quantum ESPRESSO to be incorporated into simple black-box procedural operations that can be easily executed on cloud and exascale machines.

Schrödinger (<https://www.schrodinger.com>) integrated Quantum ESPRESSO into its Materials Science Suite to enable expanded use of first-principles simulation in industrial and academic research laboratories. The proprietary interface, developed jointly by Schrödinger and the Quantum ESPRESSO Foundation, automates complex workflows for structure generation, calculations, and analysis, and provides a comprehensive graphical user interface for streamlined calculation set-up, job control, and results analysis, enabling *ab-initio* modeling of bulk materials, their surfaces, and interfaces.

Software for Chemistry & Materials B.V. (SCM) (<https://www.scm.com>) includes an interface to Quantum ESPRESSO in their Amsterdam Modeling Suite.

Synopsys (<https://www.synopsys.com>) also offers an interface to Quantum ESPRESSO in one of its simulation software products, the QuantumATK Nanolab GUI. The interface offers much more basic features than the products presented above, enabling the generation of input files using interactive scripter, read and plot charge densities, DOS and band structures, and import trajectories generated by Quantum ESPRESSO.

Materials Square (<https://www.materialsquare.com>) offers cloud computing services based on several DFT codes, including Quantum ESPRESSO (see [link](#)). They also provide a user friendly web interface for Intuitive structure modeling, diverse visualization options, and a GUI.

Mat3ra (<https://www.mat3ra.com/>) also offers cloud computing services including Quantum ESPRESSO among other materials simulation codes (see [link](#)).

Rescale (<https://rescale.com>) includes both Quantum ESPRESSO and SIESTA in their offer of cloud computing services (see [link](#)).

5. Synergies with the European institutions and ecosystem

MaX strengthens collaborations within the European HPC landscape and beyond to contribute to a robust and interconnected ecosystem for materials discovery and innovation across Europe and worldwide. MaX regularly forges collaborations with other scientific, research, industrial, and HPC-related projects and organisations to share knowledge, resources, and expertise. Here we describe some of the ongoing collaborations that MaX is currently engaged in.

5.1. The European HPC Ecosystem

The European HPC ecosystem is a collaborative network aimed at advancing high-performance computing across Europe. Supported by the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU), it fosters innovation and research by building world-class supercomputing infrastructure. These efforts are critical for ensuring Europe's leadership in scientific discovery, industrial competitiveness, and addressing societal challenges.

As in the previous phases, MaX aims at being one of the driving forces within the European HPC ecosystem. MaX leverages the European HPC infrastructures to enable progress and innovations in materials science. By working closely with other projects in the HPC and scientific communities, MaX ensures advancement both in academia and industry. The CoE and its Coordinator continuously adapted the collaboration activities, both on policy and technical issues, to the changing scenario and to the evolving ecosystem. Below is a (non-exhaustive) list of institutions, networks, projects and groups with which MaX interacts, both in the broad European ecosystem of HPC and within the materials domain. The interactions often include joint projects, workshops, training events and the like, as reported in the next paragraphs and in WP5 deliverables.

European HPC ecosystem

- [European Commission](#)
- [EuroHPC JU](#)
- [Prace](#)
- [ETP4HPC](#)
- [European Open Science Cloud](#)
- [EPI](#)
- [CASTIEL 2](#)

Materials Domain-specific ecosystem

- [Battery2030+](#)
- [Bigdata](#)
- [Big-Map](#)
- [CECAM](#)
- [DAEMON](#)
- [EMMC](#)
- [ETSF](#)
- [EuMaster4HPC](#)
- [GO FAIR](#)
- [HANAMI](#)
- [NCCR MARVEL](#)
- [MMM Hub](#)
- [OPTIMADE](#)
- [Psi-k](#)

5.2. Interaction and participation in CASTIEL2

Especially important and relevant for MaX in connection with the European HPC ecosystem is CASTIEL2, the EuroHPC-funded Coordination and Supporting Action (2023-2025 | Grant Agreement n. 101102047) gathering the National Competence Centres (NCCs) and the Centres of Excellence (CoEs) in High Performance Computing (HPC). CASTIEL2 mission is to identify and address the skills gaps in the European HPC ecosystem while harmonising the activities of the NCCs and the CoEs into a pan-European network. The effort of CASTIEL2 is targeted at promoting and nurturing collaborations between the NCCs and the CoEs to amplify their impact within the EuroHPC ecosystem. All CoEs are compelled to collaborate with CASTIEL2 and invest a relevant effort to actively contribute to the common mission through the exchange of knowledge, expertise, and best practices between HPC researchers and technologists, users, policy makers, and communication specialists.

The interactions and participation of MaX with CASTIEL2 during the first two years of the project have been described in detail in Deliverable D7.5. Here, we explain the impact of these actions.

Coordination collaboration: CASTIEL2 is organized in 5 work packages and routinely sets up interactions among all participants. As other NCCs and CoEs, MaX has appointed a “Champion” and a deputy person to attend the regular meetings of each WP, and to contribute to collaborative actions. **Impact:** MaX has contributed and participated in the governance of CASTIEL 2 through the election of Luisa Neri (CNR) as CoE deputy member of CAB “Competence Centres and CoE Advisory Board”.

NCCs/CoEs Networking and Mapping of Competences, Codes, and Services: with the involvement of all partners and the coordination of Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano) as point of contact between MaX CoE and CASTIEL2. **Impact:** This coordination has been instrumental in deploying the Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment of the MaX codes, described elsewhere in this document.

Training: with the involvement of all partners and the coordination of Daniele Varsano (CNR-Nano) as point of contact for the implementation of joint events and training activities. In the effort of building a new generation of users and boosting the impact of training activities, CASTIEL2 WP3 is trying to coordinate existing training actions about codes and their deployment in HPC machines and pushing the development of new shared initiatives. **Impact:** MaX has maintained individual connections with the NCCs that have led to the organization of the following events:

- online workshop “Efficient materials modelling on HPC with Quantum ESPRESSO, SIESTA and Yambo” 11-15/03/2024, organised by NCC Sweden and MaX (CNR/ICN2/SISSA);
- online tutorial “PWTk: a scripting interface for Quantum ESPRESSO” 20-24/05/2024, 2024, organised by MaX (IJS and SISSA) and NCC Slovenia;
- online “MaX school: materials and molecular modelling with Quantum ESPRESSO” 19-21/06/2024, organised by NCC Czechia and MaX (SISSA) with involvement of NCC Austria, Slovakia, Slovenia, Poland, and Hungary;
- MaX workshop “Modeling of (nano)materials with Quantum ESPRESSO” at the Croatian HPC Competence Centre Day on 12-13/11/2024 in Zagreb (HR), organised by MaX (IJS and SISSA) and NCC Croatia.
- Siesta school 2024, 11-15/11/2024 organized by MaX (ICN2) with involvement of NCC Spain.

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Communication and dissemination actions: with the involvement of all partners and the coordination of Marina Corradini (ICN2) as point of contact to build engaging common activities and novel outreach experiences to find new ways to reach out to different audiences. **Impacts:**

- **CASTIEL2 “Code of the Month” webinar featuring MaX Lighthouse code SIESTA:** The CASTIEL2 “Code of the Month” webinar series is dedicated to showcase the CoEs software capabilities and performances and make them accessible to a broad community of users both in academia and industry. In the December 2024 edition of the series, MaX was invited to present one of its lighthouse codes: "SIESTA - a DFT code for large scale computational material science in HPC environments" (held online on December 11, 2024). [Webinar recordings](#) are available in the MaX YouTube channel (courtesy of CASTIEL2). The webinar was presented by MaX partner and founder developer of the SIESTA code, Pablo Ordejón (CSIC Research Professor and ICN2 Group Leader and Director). The webinar attracted 59 registered attendees and 28 participants from different organizations including NCCs, CoEs, other EU-funded projects, as well as participants not involved in European projects or initiatives (see Figure 5.1). The recordings uploaded on the MaX YouTube channel have reached more than 144 views (accessed on January 28, 2025) since the day of publication of the video.
- MaX regularly contributes to the content production for the **CASTIEL2 social networks** (Figure 5.2-left) and the **CASTIEL2 “NCCs & CoEs Joint Newsletter”** (Figure 5.2-right) supporting the growing of CASTIEL2 digital reach while maximizing the dissemination of MaX advances and achievements beyond our own channels.
- MaX is involved in the **‘Supercomputing in Europe’ podcast**, a joint communication activity between CoEs and NCCs, and coordinated by EuroCC-Sweden. The aim of the podcast is to provide insights into the latest developments, applications, and future directions of the HPC technologies in the European ecosystem.

In addition to the Castiel2 activities, MaX has continued to interact with most of the other CoEs on specific joint activities (described in the deliverables of the technical WPs) as well as coordinated policies. To this end MaX has systematically participated and actively contributed to the HPC3 monthly meetings of CoE directors.

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Figure 5.1: CASTIEL2 “Code of the Month” on SIESTA: Attendees’ affiliation sorted by type of organization (top) and by type of project (bottom).

HPC CoE
 531 followers
 2mo •

Upcoming Workshop!

Modeling of (nano)materials with Quantum ESPRESSO
 12/11/2024
 09:00-17:00
 Zagreb (HR)

Registration: <https://lnkd.in/d6ejHQtw>
 Deadline November 11, 2024, at 11:00 AM.

Organized by MaX, IJS, SISSA, in collaboration with EuroCC Croatia (SRCE), within the framework of the “Croatian #HPC Competence Center Day”.

The workshop will provide participants with practical knowledge and experience in the use of #HPC and hashtag#quantum technologies.

More information at: <https://lnkd.in/dHGMCsTZ>

CASTIEL project
 Quantum ESPRESSO Foundation

Prijave na Dan Hrvatskog centra kompetencija za HPC - 12. 11. 2024.
hpc-cc.hr

4 likes • 1 repost

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Want to keep up with the latest from the European HPC Centers of excellence? Make sure to check out our newsletter!

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You'll get:

- An overview of achievements including benchmarking, success stories, and code deployments
- Links to recent publications of best practice guides and journal articles
- A summary of upcoming events including an open call for abstracts

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BioExcel CoE, Center of Excellence in Exascale CFD, ChESEE
 CoE, ESIWACE3, EXCELLERAT, HiDALGO2 Project, MaX Centre for Materials at the exascale, MultiXscale, SPACE Centre of Excellence, EoCoE Centre of Excellence: HPC for energy, Performance Optimisation and Productivity (POP)

NEWSLETTER #1

Supporting EU Excellence in HPC

CoE European Excellence in HPC Applications

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Figure 5.2: Example of social media content published on CASTIEL2 social networks (left); Example of contribution to the CASTIEL2 “NCCs & CoEs Joint Newsletter” (right).

5.3. Impact on promoting and supporting other projects

Throughout the first 24 months, MaX contributed to designing and conducting some new **initiatives with impact on the European HPC and Materials research context**. Among these we mention:

EU-Japan collaboration in HPC

As part of the EU [Digital Partnership](#) strategy with Japan, MaX was invited by the EC to help co-organize preparatory meetings between the European and Japanese research communities –especially those associated with Riken and Fugaku– in the Materials domain. The MaX director co-led several informal meetings and workshops which identified relevant stakeholders in Japan, with specific interest in sharing expertise on advanced HPC challenges and code development.

A follow up of these efforts is the ongoing [Hanami project](#), funded by the EuroHPC JU. In Hanami, Materials is one of the three Scientific Areas, where several MaX partners are playing a leading role. The evolution and global impact of MaX codes, as well as their contribution to key scientific challenges, have been growing significantly thanks to the exchanges promoted by Hanami.

EuMaster4HPC

[EuMaster4HPC](#) is a project funded by the EuroHPC JU to support MSci level education and training in HPC and its applications to HPDA and AI. It has been supporting two cohorts of Master students graduating from six awarding universities. Within the project, MaX has contributed to the definition of the MSci curriculum, especially in connection with data and applications, and to the offer of stages for the students. In addition, MaX partners are contributing to a specific Task on the analysis of the current offer of HPC training within European masters in scientific disciplines (e.g. MSci in Physics, Chemistry, Engineering etc) which have a computational curriculum. A pilot investigation of computational courses and teaching resources in the Materials domain is currently ongoing.

AI Factories

The [AI Factories](#) are currently being established to acquire new or upgrade existing EuroHPC supercomputers with AI capabilities, create supercomputing services in AI, and develop AI-oriented skills support. The EuroHPC JU announced in December the seven consortia selected to establish the first AI Factories around Europe. BSC and CINECA, both members of MaX, were two of them, involving Portugal, Romania and Türkiye and Spain in the case of BSC, and Austria, Slovenia and Italy in the case

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of CINECA. MaX is collaborating with HPC Centres hosting prospective AI factories to identify the needs and activities of relevance to the Materials research communities.

Partnership on Innovative Advanced Materials for Europe and related projects

Following the [EC Communication on Advanced Materials for Industrial Leadership](#), a number of initiatives are being launched, mostly within the framework of the co-programmed Partnership on Innovative Advanced Materials for Europe (IAM4EU). MaX and its partners contribute to the ongoing debate on the Strategic Research Agenda ([SRIA](#)), and especially on shaping the proposals of future calls for a federated digital infrastructure for materials (“Materials Commons”) and on AI foundation models for materials and preparing competitive consortia for these calls. In the case of the “Materials Commons” initiative, this is being done in active coordination with the representatives of the ministries of their respective countries, which must provide the mandate to the potential beneficiaries of the project.

6. Communication and Dissemination Actions and their Impact

6.1. Website

The project’s website has been operational since 2016 and is accessible at <https://www.max-centre.eu/>. The content of the website is continuously updated and reviewed thanks to the contributions of the consortium members. The content uploaded is managed and edited by WP5, WP6, and WP7. Selected sections are shared through social media channels, to increase the website’s visibility and attract the MaX digital community both on topics of general interest (e.g., upcoming events and trainings, latest scientific publications) and on technical/scientific content (e.g., updates related to the advances of the project, latest releases of MaX lighthouse codes, latest achievements on the deployments of MaX codes on EuroHPC machines, etc.).

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Highlights from MaX website			
Funding period	Month	Cumulative # of Unique visitors	Monthly visitors
MaX2	<i>end of MaX2</i>	33,560	5,593
2024	M24	86,443	7,204
Target	M24	-	> 6,000

Key website sections

MaX Software: in this section, we showcase the MaX lighthouse codes. Each code section comes with a description of the code features and functionalities, as well as useful links redirecting to the code download, documentation, users forum, tutorials, and GitLab. **The MaX Software section reaches more than 150 monthly visits on average.**

Impact of MaX lighthouse codes: This section showcases the usage of the MaX codes among the scientific community both across Europe and worldwide. The section displays two types of maps (world-view and Europe), where there are reported records of peer-reviewed papers citing the MaX codes, divided by country. We also show in an histogram the citation growth per code over time. **Section “Impact of MaX lighthouse codes” reaches 37 monthly visits on average.**

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MaX applications on EuroHPC supercomputers

MaX lighthouse codes—QUANTUM ESPRESSO, YAMBO, SIESTA, BigDFT and FLEUR— are efficient parallel codes with a demonstrated capability to scale on homogeneous nodes up to several thousand MPI ranks by adopting multiple levels of parallelism. In its third phase, MaX is working to step up the scalability of its lighthouse codes to make them able to exploit efficiently up to several thousand CPUs. At the same time, we continue to add new features, plugins, and data exchange methods.

The figure below shows where we are today. MaX lighthouse applications are running on heterogeneous EuroHPC systems with high parallel efficiency. In many cases they are deployed and the modules are available to users (M, dark green), or demonstrated by the developers and ready for installation (D). Almost all architectures are now supported (S) and are ready for automatic deployment. EuroHPC Continuous Integration - Continuous Deployment procedures (C/CD) are in the design and development phase; collaborations with CASTIEL2, other CoEs, and the Hosting Entities (HPC centres) are underway.

Throughout the entire project lifetime, MaX will continue to deploy its lighthouse codes on pre- and exascale machines of the European HPC ecosystem, allowing users to solve outstanding scientific problems at unprecedented scales and degree of accuracy.

Exascale: in this section we build knowledge and keep our community updated about exascale related topics and challenges, as well as the latest advances of MaX in exploiting the most recent HPC systems. In particular, in this page we regularly disseminate information about the deployment status of MaX software across the EuroHPC architectures. **The Exascale section on the website reaches more than 100 monthly visits on average.**

News & Events: This is the entrance door to our website, where we regularly share information with a dual purpose: (i) to redirect our target audiences to visit other key pages of our website; (ii) to encourage our target audiences to make return visits to our website for regular updates. This helps us boost our website's search engine rankings and visibility. Between M1 and M24, MaX has created 83 items for the News & Events section of the website addressing a variety of topics (see image below). **The News & Events section reaches 1K monthly visits on average.** Below are some examples of different News & Events published in the MaX webpage.

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1. Promotion of consortium partners' participation at conferences.

2. Promotion of latest scientific publications.

3. Promotion of upcoming training programmes.

4. Promotion of latest releases of MaX codes.

5. General topics of interest in the EuroHPC ecosystem.

Communication KIT: where communication material produced during the project's lifetime is regularly uploaded and stored. The Communication KIT is available to all partners to download, print, and distribute in the events they join or organize. **The Communication KIT reaches more than 100 monthly visits on average.**

Corporate flyer with an overview of the MaX project, its mission and vision, and its consortium partners. **Distributed at:** ISC High Performance 2024 in Hamburg and at SC24 in Atlanta (US).

Technical poster with the results achieved in the First Reporting Period (M1-M12). **Showcased at:** Euro HPC Summit Week 2024, 18-21 March, 2024 - Antwerp (BE).

Technical brochure gathering the latest performance and scalability results of the MaX codes. **Showcased at:** Second EuroHPC User Day, 22-23 October, 2024 - Amsterdam (NL).

Training and education: in this section we gather a wide range of freely accessible educational material produced under WP5 in the HPC and materials science domain for each MaX code. The training materials include the online courses and schools, lectures, workshops, and webinars

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organized by MaX members under the coordination of WP5. Most recent video lectures and training materials are available on the [Lhumos](#) e-learning platform, accessible since January 2024. **The Training section reaches more than 100 monthly visits on average.**

Web Impact: As outlined in the D6.1 - Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan submitted in M6, the targeted KPI for the website is to reach 6000+ monthly website visits. After three consecutive funded periods, today the MaX website reaches 7000+ monthly visits on average thanks to the content regularly updated and relevant for the MaX digital community. It is expected that this number will continue to increase, as the project advances and more results will be available and shared on the website, besides being further promoted on social media channels from which visitors will be redirected to the website.

6.2. Social Media Channels

MaX social media channels play a key role in building and strengthening MaX online presence, as they allow us to communicate project outputs while engaging with our different target audiences. To support these efforts, MaX uses X (@max_center2), LinkedIn (@max-centre), and YouTube (@MaXCentreeXascale). Each platform aligns within the communication strategy as described in the following sections. At the beginning of 2025, MaX opened a BlueSky account (@max-coe.bsky.social) and plans to leave the X account.

MaX X channel

X user base predominantly gathers male audiences, with ages between 25 and 34 years old. X users use the platform for different purposes including entertainment and as a way to stay informed/as a news resource. Content on the platform (tweets) is structured to encourage concise communication that quickly captures attention and is easily digestible for users scrolling through their feeds. This brevity allows for immediate engagement, making X the ideal platform for sharing quick information without demanding too much time or focus from the audience.

MaX LinkedIn channel

LinkedIn started as a social network mainly used for job-seeking but has now evolved into a platform for networking, staying updated on industry news, and celebrating the milestones of colleagues. Today, LinkedIn attracts professionals seeking industry-specific content and networking opportunities. Content production on the platform is structured to facilitate long-form posts and in-depth discussions. Tools like hashtags and tags help spread content and engage kindred accounts and pages. MaX LinkedIn page predominantly gathers professionals interested in industry-related discussions,

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training programmes, and networking, making it an influential platform for MaX. Demographics on our LinkedIn community is presented in **Annex 2**.

For X and LinkedIn, the content production covers a broad range of topics/categories and includes:

1		<p>“Meet our Partners” campaign, to raise the visibility of the partner institutes involved in the MaX consortium and engage with their audiences.</p>
2		<p>Promotion of MaX Training events.</p>
3		<p>Promotion of scientific events, organized or attended by MaX partners.</p>
4		<p>Promotion of scientific papers published by the MaX partners within the MaX framework.</p>
5		<p>Promotion of activities organized by partners/collaborators within the EuroHPC ecosystem and beyond.</p>

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As outlined in the *D6.1 Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan* submitted in M6, our primary goal of using social media channels is to expand our reach and engage a wide range of digital audiences. In this context, the **number of posts** published on MaX X and LinkedIn channels is used as an indicator of our effort towards our goal. **Follower Growth (%)** is used as a KPI to measure effectiveness in expanding the MaX digital community. In addition, we present the **Mean Engagement Rate (%)** for X and LinkedIn as a key indicator of the relevance and impact of our content among our digital audience. Below, we present the analysis of MaX social media platforms during the first two years of the project. For the two platforms, we show the starting metrics at M1 (January 2023) and the cumulative metrics reached at M12 (December 2023) and M24 (December 2024).

Highlights from X					
Year	Month	Cumulative # of posts	Cumulative # of Followers	Cumulative Follower Growth (%)	Mean Engagement Rate (%)
<i>starting metrics</i>	M1	-	1381	-	-
2023	M12	169	1515	9.7	4.7
2024	M24	419	1590	15.1	5.0
Target	M24	220	2072	50	0.05

Highlights from LinkedIn					
Year	Month	Cumulative # of posts	Cumulative # of Followers	Cumulative Follower Growth (%)	Mean Engagement Rate (%)
<i>starting metrics</i>	M1	-	691	-	-
2023	M12	91	962	39.2	7.2
2024	M24	285	1635	137	8.8
Target	M24	120	1037	50	3.8

Focus on: “Women in the eXascale era” Social Media Campaign

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To increase the visibility of the women scientists involved in MaX, we launched a Social Media Campaign with the occasion of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science - February 11. The campaign started on February 11, 2023 and ran for 7 weeks. It consisted of 7 posts where we highlighted the contribution and career paths of the women scientists working in MaX. The campaign was published both on X and on LinkedIn, reaching 4.8% and 8.7% engagement rate respectively.

Screenshots of the “Women in the eXascale era” social media campaign.

MaX YouTube channel

YouTube is the second-most visited website on the internet. Therefore, we use it as a broad dissemination platform to raise awareness about MaX goals and achievements. The content of the MaX YouTube channel is additionally promoted through MaX X and LinkedIn platforms to help engage followers across various touchpoints. Today, MaX YouTube channel counts 178 videos included in 17 Playlists. Demographics on the MaX YouTube community is presented in Annex 2. The videos are general ones that present the main objectives of the projects, recording of events organized and attended by the MaX team (like the webinar series on codes) and video lectures of training courses and schools. In the third phase of the project, MaX has uploaded on its YouTube channel the following content:

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<p>1</p>		<p>Meet the MaX Centre of Excellence - Phase 3, 2023-2026 (#1)</p>
<p>2</p>		<p>HPC, HTC, and Data Analytics for Materials Discovery and Design (#1)</p>
<p>3</p>		<p>MaX CoE Barcelona Meeting: Charting the Exascale Computing Future for Materials Science (#1)</p>
<p>4</p>		<p>Video-interviews with key MaX members describing the technical challenges of MaX3 (#5)</p>
<p>5</p>		<p>Videolectures (#16) of MaX Training School: “Ab-initio many-body perturbation theory: from equilibrium to time-resolved spectroscopies and nonlinear optics “</p>

As outlined in the *D6.1 Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination Plan* submitted in M6, our primary goal of using YouTube is to expand even further our reach and engage a wide range of audiences on different platforms. In this context, the number of videos published on the MaX YouTube channel is used as an indicator of our effort towards our goal. Subscribers Growth (%) is used as a KPI to measure effectiveness in expanding the MaX digital community. For YouTube we evaluate the Average Viewed (%) metric, which is the average percentage of a video that a viewer watched before clicking out or stopping. The average viewed metric gives us a measure of the audience engagement toward the video content. Below, we present the analysis of the MaX YouTube channel during the first two years of the project. We show the starting metrics at M1 (January 2023) and the cumulative metrics reached at M12 (December 2023) and M24 (December 2024).

Highlights from YouTube					
Year	Month	Cumulative # of videos	Cumulative # of Subscribers	Cumulative Subscribers Growth (%)	Average Viewed (%)
<i>starting metrics</i>	M1	-	441	-	-
2023	M12	2	691	56.7	38.5
2024	M24	9	774	75.5	35.3
Target	M24	10	662	50	50

Impact: In the first two years of the project, MaX has dedicated a huge effort in social media content production, reflected in the number of original posts realized and published on X and LinkedIn, and on the number of videos produced and published on YouTube. This effort has translated into an increase of the number of followers/subscribers on our three digital channels. In particular, the **follower growth on X has increased slower than envisaged, whereas the follower growth on LinkedIn and the subscribers' growth on YouTube have exceeded the mid-term target.** The engagement rate reflects how well our content resonates with our audience. **Both X and LinkedIn show high engagement rates, exceeding the average engagement rates of those platforms. This suggests that we are targeting a niche community in computer and materials sciences, and that our content is both appealing and relevant for them.** It is worth mentioning that our LinkedIn page is the top social media channel attracting people/users interested in MaX Training programmes. As a matter of fact, the promotion of MaX training through the LinkedIn page is the one followers interact the most with. On YouTube, the *average percentage viewed* is a measure of the audience retention and its value depends on the video's length and content. YouTube analytics indicate that the typical view duration on the channel is approximately 50% (in other words, viewers generally watch about half of a video, on average). MaX

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YouTube content reaches a lower-than-average engagement on the platform. This gives us pointers on how to improve our future videos, both in terms of duration and/or type of content.

6.3. Newsletter

In the evolving digital landscape, MaX continually explores innovative ways to reach out to our audiences. As part of its content strategy, in July 2024 MaX launched its LinkedIn Newsletter. LinkedIn Newsletter is a recent feature proposed by the platform that is gaining attention. There are three advantages of using LinkedIn Newsletter:

- when a user follows our page, they are automatically invited to follow our Newsletter;
- when a visitor subscribes to our newsletter, they automatically become a follower of our page;
- LinkedIn Newsletters are SEO searchable and can be found in Google Search.

This strategy helps us grow our LinkedIn followers and Newsletter subscribers base within the same channel/platform, while being visible on the internet. MaX LinkedIn Newsletter is published monthly and is structured to touch on multiple subjects:

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<p>1</p>	<p>MaX releases the latest results on the performance and scalability of its lighthouse codes</p> <p>MaX has published its latest 'Performance and Scalability' brochure, presenting comprehensive results on the performance and scaling of its lighthouse codes across diverse EuroHPC architectures. The brochure was showcased at the Second EuroHPC User Day 2024. The brochure provides an in-depth look at the latest advancements of MaX lighthouse codes in achieving performance and scalability to harness the full capabilities of HPC for materials science research. Download a copy of the brochure and read more about its release.</p>	<p>Latest news about MaX codes and performance.</p>
<p>2</p>	<p>MaX school: Fleur Hands-on tutorial 2024 edition</p> <p>Attended by 47 registered participants from all over the world, the school offered hands-on sessions to learn the use of the MaX lighthouse code FLEUR. Attendees had the chance to interact with the code developers and showcase their results in a dedicated poster session. Recorded material is available in the program of the school. Selected lectures will be available soon on Lhumos.</p>	<p>Past training events organized by MaX with the link to the recorded training material.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>MaX joins the Second EuroHPC User Day</p> <p>Organised by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking and the EuroCC Netherlands. MaX Coordinator Elisa Molinari (CNR-Nano and UNIMORE) and Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA) will represent MaX at the Second EuroHPC User Day. MaX will host one of the Tables in the special session for users called "Walk-in networking sessions focusing on specific EuroHPC user needs: provide your feedback and get some advice." (October 23, between 10:30-12:00 am). Find out more in the Preliminary programme.</p>	<p>Past conferences attended by MaX members.</p>

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Upcoming trainings on MaX codes and upcoming events attended by MaX.

The format of the newsletter includes *teasers* (short paragraphs) with external links redirecting to longer news, typically on our website, or to further readings available on other MaX platforms. This is done on purpose, as readers only glance at the content and do not read it thoroughly. Hence, our slim structure facilitates the newsletter scanning (the average time allocated to reading a newsletter is 52 seconds) and encourages readers to visit our website. Below, we present the analysis of MaX LinkedIn Newsletter performance between July - December 2024. We show the number of subscribers, the article views, the members reached, and the engagement rate.

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Impact: MaX LinkedIn Newsletter started from scratch in July 2024 (M18). Since its first publication, **the Newsletter has been steadily gaining subscribers as new releases were published**. The first newsletter release was broadly spread among our LinkedIn community and reached the entire pool of our page followers. Throughout the time, as new newsletter releases were published, the reach of the newsletter flattened to the *niche* of target audience that is most interested in following our updates. Article views oscillate depending on the newsletter release. On average, each release was accessed and read at least by half of our subscribers. **Since its first release, the newsletter engagement rate has always been well beyond 3%, meaning that the content resonates very well with our readers.**

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6.4. MaX 'Performance and Scalability' Brochure

In October 2024, MaX published a [technical brochure](#) presenting the latest results on the performance and scaling of its lighthouse codes across diverse EuroHPC architectures. The brochure is a valuable resource for computational and materials scientists seeking to use HPC resources to solve complex scientific problems in a variety of fields including nanotechnology, energy, and materials design. The brochure is accessible on MaX website and free to download: [Performance and Scalability of MaX lighthouse codes](#). **Since October 2024, more than 50 visitors have accessed the brochure online.** The brochure's first showcase occurred at the Second EuroHPC User Day, during a special session titled *“Walk-in networking sessions focusing on specific EuroHPC user needs: provide your feedback and get some advice.”* (October 23, between 10:30-12:00 am), where MaX Coordinator Elisa Molinari (CNR-Nano and UNIMORE) and Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA) interacted with the community of users of the EuroHPC ecosystem.

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Brochure Promotion on MaX digital channels

The release of the technical brochure was further promoted through a dedicated News on MaX website: [Just released! Performance & Scalability of MaX lighthouse codes](#). **Since October 2024, the News has been read by more than 340 visitors.** The brochure was also promoted on the MaX LinkedIn channel. The promotion consisted of a pinned post on MaX LinkedIn page (the post appears at the top of the page for any visitors) and dedicated posts published regularly throughout the month to redirect visitors to our website and the brochure download page. **Since October 2024, the pinned post on MaX LinkedIn page has been seen by 260 LinkedIn users with a 9.2% engagement rate.**

6.5. MaX training programs

MaX training initiatives aim at equipping computational materials scientists and industry professionals with the advanced skills required for the evolving landscape of HPC, especially as Europe advances toward exascale computing under the EuroHPC JU. Focused on bridging the HPC skills gap, MaX offers a wide range of programs, from hands-on workshops and hackathons to university-level lectures.

These efforts are complemented by bespoke training sessions for beginners/entry level and more experienced end-users, highlighting MaX commitment to tailored skill development. A detailed report of the activities done so far within the MaX training program has been presented in Deliverable 5.2 First report on MAX training events (submitted in December 2024).

Training events, directly organized or supported by MaX, are central to diffuse the use of MaX lighthouse codes, particularly as the codes are now adapted for diverse HPC architectures. The shift to exascale systems demands new proficiencies from both developers and users. Thus, MaX training prioritizes the upskilling of emerging developers while enhancing user awareness to ensure efficient usage of HPC capabilities. In the past two years, domain-specific training has provided participants with theoretical insights into MaX methodologies, alongside hands-on experience in best practices for HPC applications.

MaX has also embraced accessibility and collaboration in its training approach. With both online and in-person sessions, participants gain practical experience in diverse settings. Hackathons facilitate engagement between novice and seasoned developers, fostering a collaborative learning environment. A majority of the training materials are made publicly accessible, expanding MaX reach to a broader audience. The material can be accessed on different MaX digital channels: the MaX website, MaX YouTube channel, and starting from January 2024, also on the MaX section on the Lhumos platform.

6.6. Scientific Publications

In the first two years of the project, MaX has contributed to the advancement in materials and computational science research through the publication of open-access compliant, peer-reviewed scientific papers. **Between M1 and M24, MaX partners have published 35 scientific papers (20 Gold OA and 15 Green OA), including 4 peer-reviewed articles focused specifically on advancements in software capabilities and co-design optimization and 1 publication of software release.** Several of these contributions appear in top-tier journals underscoring the high impact and visibility of MaX partners work. The list of publications from months 1 to 24 can be found in Annex 3.

6.7. Stakeholders Engagement Events

In the first two years of the project, MaX consortium has actively participated in more than 93 events (51 events attended in 2023 and 42 in 2024) to stay abreast of the developments in HPC and materials science. MaX partners have engaged in a variety of third-party events, including workshops, conferences, coordination meetings, and public outreach events organized by external organizations, both at national and international level (see infographic below). MaX participation in such events has strengthened the project's presence and brand recognition and fostered connections with our different target audiences. This presence has enabled MaX to raise awareness of its major

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advancements through targeted presentations delivered by the project partners. The detailed list of events attended by MaX partners in 2023 and 2024 is presented in Annex 4.

Infographic: Third-party events attended by MaX partners sorted by their primary topic and target audience.

MaX sponsor of leading conferences in the materials and HPC domains

MaX sponsored 2 leading conferences in materials science and HPC, demonstrating commitment to advancing research, collaboration, and innovation in these fields within the industry and academic community. By sponsoring such conferences, MaX further strengthened its brand and reputation, and

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fostered networking, knowledge exchange, and visibility among top researchers, industry experts, and policymakers in materials and HPC.

	<p>11th International Conference on Multiscale Materials Modeling (MMM-11)</p> <p>22-27 September, 2024 Prague (CZ)</p> <p>Conference website: MMM11 – Multiscale Materials Modeling</p>
	<p>AI4AM2024: Artificial Intelligence for Advanced Materials 2024</p> <p>2-4 July, 2024 Barcelona (ES)</p> <p>Conference website: AI4AM2024</p>

7. Conclusions and perspectives

The activities of MaX during the last two years have been guided to maximize the impact of the CoE on a wide range of potential beneficiaries of the results of the project. We have identified seven target groups/communities which will use or further uptake the results of our project, and on which we aimed at having an impact:

- Users of quantum materials modelling codes,
- HPC centres,
- Code developers of other quantum materials modelling codes,
- Hardware manufacturers,
- Independent Software Vendors,
- Policy makers and society at large,
- Industry.

While the first six communities were already identified and reflected in our original proposal and the Grant Agreement, the last one (Industry) has been added after the commencement of the project, to highlight the importance we give to the up-take and impact of our codes on the industry.

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We see the efforts of MaX as structured across two key domains: Software for next-generation computing, and Scientific grand challenges for global societal and industrial needs. In the first 24 months of the project, we have concentrated mainly on developing the tools to advance in these two domains, and more specifically, on ensuring that our software (scientific codes, modules and libraries, but also workflows and data, and even the processes for software engineering, CI/CD, etc) is ready for the exascale challenge.

A main outcome of the work done so far is the deployment of MaX codes on existing EuroHPC infrastructures. We have installed, deployed and benchmarked the five MaX lighthouse codes on practically all of the EuroHPC machines and partitions. This is strongly impacting the community of users of our codes, who are able to access these infrastructures for their R&D projects, and to make efficient use of the widely different architectures available.

We have also incorporated best practices in software engineering, also addressing issues relevant for, e.g., continuous integration (CI) and continuous deployment (CD). At the same time, we have advanced in the modularization and separation of concerns in our codes, developing modules and libraries which can be used by other codes. This is having an important impact outside the consortium, as it has allowed us to integrate our developments (modules and libraries) in other projects.

Co-development activities have been centred around the energy efficiency of MaX codes. We have been able to obtain significant reductions in energy consumption (up to 25%) with a very modest degradation in the time-to-solution, in several architectures, by static tuning of the CPU clock frequencies before the application execution. These results should guide HPC centres and code users to adapt their execution parameters to reduce the energy footprint of the MaX codes.

Workflows are a key component of the exploitation of pre- and exascale machines. MaX has continued developing the infrastructure to manage complex workflows in materials science, at the same time as specific workflows for the grand challenges included in our proposal (in the areas of green energy, health and information technologies). The scientific impact enabled by MaX on these grand challenges will be even more visible in the second part of the project, when they are fully deployed. The impact of the development of frameworks for workflow development and management can be now gauged by the number of plugins and workflows deposited in the AiiDA Registry, which has experienced an increase of nearly 50% since the beginning of the current MaX project.

Data is expected to be one of the cornerstones of the future research and discovery of materials. The Materials Cloud infrastructure is a key instrument in the archiving and dissemination of raw and curated data for materials science, along with data analytic tools and educational resources. Materials Cloud has an important impact in the community, receiving some 20,000 visits per month, and having reached a milestone of 1,000 publications in its Archive repository.

In the last two years we have witnessed increasing interest for MaX from **AI-related projects and communities**. Data from MaX flagship codes are being exploited to feed the training process in Machine Learning applications (e.g. training of force fields from ab-initio data). However, the interaction of AI with our activity goes way further: AI techniques are used in various ways to accelerate electronic structure calculations. MaX codes are proving essential to enable these very dynamic research lines. Meanwhile, we are promoting research conferences and summer schools, as well as new projects/initiatives within the EuroHPC and Materials domains. We expect that the impact

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associated with AI/ML will further grow in the next years of MaX, as we will report more extensively in the years to come.

A crucial impact of MaX is the adoption of its flagship codes by the academic and industrial users. We have shown in this deliverable how widespread is the use of our codes by measuring the number of scientific articles citing the MaX codes, the geographic distribution of these citations, and the number of patents filed using the codes. In 2024, we reached 40,000 publications citing the MaX codes' reference papers, an impressive amount by any measure of scientific impact. To give an idea of the magnitude of this number, the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble (France), one of the largest experimental scientific facilities in Europe, has produced 37,000 publications since its inauguration in 1994.

The industrial impact goes beyond incorporating the MaX codes in the materials discovery pipelines of the industry. It also contributes to creating an ecosystem where Independent Software Vendors can create added value products for their customers, around the free and open source MaX codes. Several companies (some of them created around the communities of MaX partners) are developing business models built around free open source codes, by providing utilities like GUIs, workflows, job management platforms, data storage and cloud computing services. The economic value of these products is hard to assess, but the growing number of commercial products which link to the MaX codes is growing at a fast pace, which is a clear sign of potential profitability.

MaX has been very active in contributing to the European ecosystem of HPC, in the materials domain and beyond. We have been a very active member of CASTIEL2, contributing to the deployment of Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment in our codes, participating also in a large number of training and dissemination events. Besides, MaX has had a direct impact on some EU initiatives: the EU-Japan collaboration on HPC (which led to the Hanami project funded by the EuroHPC JU, with the participation of several MaX groups and their codes), the EuMaster4HPC, the AI Factories, and the Partnership on Innovative Advanced Materials for Europe (IAM4EU).

To disseminate the activities of MaX and to maximize their impact, we have deployed a battery of communication and dissemination actions and tools, including a strong online presence (website, social media, electronic newsletter, etc), electronic and printed materials (like the brochure describing the performance and scaling benchmarks of our codes), and training programs. Scientific publications, as the main dissemination channel of scientific results, amount to 35 papers in the first 24 months of the project, several of them in top-tier journals. Finally, we have participated in more than 93 events, and co-sponsored 2 leading conferences in materials science and HPC.

In conclusion, the first two years of MaX have achieved a high level of impact on several target communities, an impact which should increase as the project evolves during the next months. The strategic importance of R&D&I on materials is clearly growing, especially in the European Union, and MaX is well positioned to contribute in providing accurate, efficient and competitive simulation software tools that can leverage the growing HPC capabilities of the EU in this critical field.

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8. Annexes

8.1. Annex 1: Companies that cite the MaX codes in their scientific publications.

The following list contains names of companies which appear in the affiliations of scientific publications that cite the MaX flagship codes among their references. We have found a total of 225 such entries, which are a relevant measure of the widespread usage of the MaX codes in the ecosystem of companies and industrial users. Source: Web of Science.

ABB	Boehringer Ingelheim
AC2T Research GmbH	Boeing
AGC Inc	Bosch
AMO GMBH	Boston Consulting Group (BCG)
ARCTOS	Bruker AXS GmbH
ASM International	Bruker BioSpin GmbH
ASML Holding	Bruker Corporation
Aerospace Corporation - USA	CSL
Air Liquide	Callaghan Innovation
Air Products & Chemicals	Canon Incorporated
Albemarle Corporation	Carl Zeiss AG
Alcatel-Lucent	China Aerospace Science & Industry Corp.
Apple Inc	China Electronics Technology Group
Applied Materials Inc	China National Nuclear Corporation
ArcelorMittal	China National Petroleum Corporation
Areva	China National Tobacco Corporation
Asahi Kasei Corporation	China Nuclear Power Engineering Co Ltd.
Aselsan	China Southern Power Grid
Astex Pharmaceuticals	China Telecom Corp. Ltd.
AstraZeneca	China Three Gorges Corporation
BASF	Cisco Systems Inc
BIOVIA	Clariant
BMW AG	Corning Inc
BP	DENSO
BYD	Daicel Corporation
Bayer AG	Daihatsu Motor Co., Ltd.
BioNTech SE	Daimler AG

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Dassault Systemes
Delphi
DuPont
ENEOS Corporation
Electricite de France (EDF)
Element Six
Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuaria
Eni SpA
Equinor
Exxon Mobil Corporation
FEI Company
Facebook Inc
Ford Motor Company
Freescale Semiconductor
Fuji Electric Co., LTD.
Fujifilm Corporation
Fujitsu Laboratories Ltd
Fujitsu Ltd
Furukawa Electric
General Electric
General Motors
Gilead Science
GlaxoSmithKline
GlobalFoundries
Google Incorporated
HRL Laboratories
Haldor Topsoe
Hewlett-Packard
High Performance Technologies, Inc.
Hitachi Limited
Honda Motor Company
Honda USA
Horiba Ltd.
Hydro-Quebec
IHI Corporation
IMST GMBH
Idemitsu Kosan
Intel Corporation Intellectual Ventures
International Business Machines (IBM)
Italfarmaco

J.A. Woollam Co.
JFE Holdings, Inc.
JFE Steel
JP Morgan Chase & Company
JSC Farmak
JSR Corporation
Japan Tobacco Inc.
Jeol Ltd
Johnson & Johnson
KLA Corporation
Kawasaki Heavy Industries
Kissei Pharmaceutical Co Ltd
Kitware, Inc.
Kobe Steel
Konica Minolta Inc.
Kyma Technologies, Inc.
Kyocera
LG Chem
LG Display
LG Electronics
Lam Research Corporation
Lenzing AG
Mars
Materials Center Leoben Forschungs GmbH
Merck KGaA
Micron Technology
Microsoft
Mineral Resources
Mitsubishi Electric Corporation
Mitsubishi Materials Corporation
Mitsubishi Tanabe Pharma Corporation
Murata Manufacturing Co Ltd
NEC Corporation
NXP Semiconductors
Nichia Corporation
Nippon Steel & Sumitomo Metal Corporation
Nippon Telegraph & Telephone Corporation
Nissan Motor Company
Nokia Corporation
Nokia Siemens Networks

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Northrop Grumman Corporation
Nova Research, Inc.
Nuclear Fuel Complex (NFC)
Nuclear Research & Consultancy Group
Nvidia Corporation
Omya International AG
Osram
POSCO
Panasonic
Paramount Global
PetroChina Company
Petrobras
Pfizer
Philip Morris International Inc
Philips
Philips Research
Plansee Holding AG
Porto Conte Ricerche Srl
Q Chem Inc.
Qinetiq Group Plc
RAFAEL ADVANCED DEFENSE SYSTEMS
Radiation Monitoring Devices
Raytheon Technologies
Renesas Electronics Corporation
Rigaku Corporation
Roche Holding
Rockwell Collins
Royal Dutch Shell
Saint Gobain SA
Samsung
Samsung Electronics
Samsung Semiconductor (SSI)
Sanofi France
Sanofi-Aventis
Saudi Aramco
Saudi Basic Industries Corporation (SABIC)
Scania
Schrodinger, Inc.
Science Applications International Corporation
Seagate Technology
Shanghai Electric
Shin-Etsu Chemical Company
Siemens AG

Siemens Germany
Sinopec
Solvay SA
Solvias
Stellantis Italy
Stellantis N.V.
STMicroelectronics
Studsvik Nuclear AB (AB Atomenergi)
Sumitomo Chem Co Ltd
Sumitomo Electric Industries
Synopsys Inc
TAE Technologies
Taiwan Semiconductor Manufacturing Comp.
Takeda Pharmaceutical Company Ltd
Tamura Corporation
Tata Consultancy Services Limited (TCS)
Tata Sons
Tata Steel Limited
Texas Instruments
Thales Group
Thermo Fisher Scientific
Tokyo Electron Ltd
TopGaN Ltd SAIC-Frederick
SANY
SAS Institute Inc
SECO Tools AB
SHT Smart High Tech AB
Toshiba Corporation
Tosoh Corporation
Total SA
Tower Semiconductor Ltd.
Toyota Central R&D Labs Inc
Toyota Motor Corporation
Trina Solar
Valeo SA
Volkswagen
Volkswagen Germany
Wacker Chemie
Weichai Power Co., Ltd.
Western Digital Corporation
XCMG Group
Yazaki
Zyvex Corporation

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8.2. Annex 2: Demographics of MaX digital communities

Demographics of MaX LinkedIn community:

Followers by country

[View table](#)

Followers by area

[View table](#)

Followers by industry

[View table](#)

Followers by functions

[View table](#)

Followers by seniority

[View table](#)

Followers by company size

[View table](#)

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Demographics of MaX YouTube community.

Gender

Age

Viewers by country

Traffic source

Source	Visitors	Percent
Direct or unknown	80	9.82%
Playlist pages	73	8.96%
Suggested videos	65	7.98%
Browser features	56	6.87%
YouTube channels	42	5.15%

8.3. Annex 3: List of MaX scientific publications

- Gold OA
- Green OA
- Software releases, advancements in software capabilities, co-design optimization

2023

- **1 Efficient GW calculations in two dimensional materials through a stochastic integration of the screened potential**, A. Guandalini, P. D'Amico, A. Ferretti, and D. Varsano, npj Computational Materials volume 9, Article number: 44 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-023-00989-7>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.11946>
- **2 Towards high-throughput many-body perturbation theory: efficient algorithms and automated workflows**, M. Bonacci, J. Qiao, N. Spallanzani, A. Marrazzo, G. Pizzi, E. Molinari, D. Varsano, A. Ferretti, and D. Prezzi, npj Comput Mater 9, 74 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-023-01027-2>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.06407>
- **3 Dielectric response and excitations of hydrogenated free-standing graphene**, M. G. Betti, D. Marchiani, A. Tonelli, M. Sbroscia, E. Blundo, M. De Luca, A. Polimeni, R. Frisenda, C. Mariani, S. Jeong, Y. Ito, N. Cavani, R. Biagi, P. N.O. Gillespie, M. A. Hernandez Bertran, M. Bonacci, E. Molinari, V. De Renzi, and D. Prezzi, Carbon Trends, 12, 100274 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cartre.2023.100274>
<https://hdl.handle.net/11573/1685773>
- **4 Quenching of low-energy optical absorption in bilayer C₃N polytypes**, M. Zanfrognini, M. Bonacci, F. Paleari, E. Molinari, A. Ruini, A. Ferretti, M. J. Caldas, and D. Varsano, Phys. Rev. Materials 7, 064006 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevMaterials.7.064006>
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2302.09261.pdf>
- **5 Efficient full frequency GW for metals using a multipole approach for the dielectric screening**, Dario A. Leon, Andrea Ferretti, Daniele Varsano, Elisa Molinari, and Claudia Cardoso, Phys. Rev. B 107, 155130 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.107.155130>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.02282>
- **6 | software | QUANTUM ESPRESSO: One Further Step toward the Exascale**, I. Carnimeo, F. Affinito, S. Baroni, O. Baseggio, L. Bellentani, R. Bertossa, P. D. Delugas, F. Ferrari Ruffino, S. Orlandini, F. Spiga, and P. Giannozzi, J. Chem. Theory Comput. (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.3c00249>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10601483/>

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- 7 Self-interaction and transport of solvated electrons in molten salts**, P. Pegolo, S. Baroni, and F. Grasselli *Journal of Chemical Physics* 159, 97, 094116 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0169474>
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2305.10052.pdf>
- 8 | software | koopmans: An Open-Source Package for Accurately and Efficiently Predicting Spectral Properties with Koopmans Functionals**, E. B. Linscott, N. Colonna, R. De Genaro, N. L. Nguyen, G. Borghi, and A. Ferretti *J. of Chem. Theory and Computation* (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.3c00652>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.07759>
- 9 Strong magnetic proximity effect in van der Waals heterostructures driven by direct hybridization**, C. Cardoso, A. T. Costa, A. H. MacDonald, and J. Fernández-Rossier, *Phys. Rev. B* 108, 184423 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.108.184423>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.16813>
- 10 Heat conductivity from energy-density fluctuations**, E. Drigo, M. G. Izzo, and S. Baroni, *J. Chem. Phys.* 159, 184107 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0168732>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.09070>
- 11 Strong Coupling of Coherent Phonons to Excitons in Semiconducting Monolayer MoTe₂**, C. J. Sayers, A. Genco, C. Trovatiello, S. Dal Conte, V. O. Khaustov, J. Cervantes-Villanueva, D. Sangalli, A. Molina-Sanchez, C. Coletti, C. Gadermaier, and G. Cerullo, *Nano Lett.*, 23, 20, 9235–9242 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.3c01936>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.07561>
- 12 Hydrodynamic finite-size scaling of the thermal conductivity in glasses**, A. Fiorentino, P. Pegolo, and S. Baroni, *npj Computational Materials* 9, 157 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-023-01116-2>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.07010>
- 13 Excitonic effects in energy loss spectra of freestanding graphene**, A. Guandalini, R. Senga, Y.-C. Lin, K. Suenaga, A. Ferretti, D. Varsano, A. Recchia, P. Barone, F. Mauri, T. Pichler, and C. Kramberger, *Nano Lett.* 2023, 23, 24, 11835–11841 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.3c03863>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.06367>
- 14 First-principles study of the gap in the spin excitation spectrum of the CrI₃ honeycomb ferromagnet**, T. Gorni, O. Baseggio, P. Delugas, I. Timrov, and S. Baroni, *Phys. Rev. B* 107, L220410 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.107.L220410>
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2212.09516.pdf>

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15 Inhibitory behaviour and adsorption stability of benzothiazole derivatives as corrosion inhibitors towards galvanised steel, Q. Deng, J. M. Castillo-Robles, E. de Freitas Martins, P. Ordejón, J.-N. Gorges, P. Eiden, X.-B. Chen, P. Keil, and I. Cole, *Mol. Syst. Des. Eng.*, 2024, Advance Article (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3ME00153A>
<https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlepdf/2024/me/d3me00153a>

16 Magnon-phonon interactions enhance the gap at the Dirac point in the spin-wave spectra of CrI3 two-dimensional magnets, P. Delugas, O. Baseggio, I. Timrov, S. Baroni, and T. Gorni, *Phys. Rev. B* 107, 214452 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.107.214452>
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2105.04531.pdf>

17 First-principles study of luminescence in hexagonal boron nitride single layer: Exciton-phonon coupling and the role of substrate, P. Lechiffart, F. Paleari, D. Sangalli, and C. Attaccalite, *Phys. Rev. Materials* 7, 024006 (2023)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevMaterials.7.024006>
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2212.10407.pdf>

18 Distinguishing different stackings in layered materials via luminescence spectroscopy, M. Zanfognini, A. Plaud, I. Stenger, F. Fossard, L. Sponza, L. Schué, F. Paleari, E. Molinari, D. Varsano, L. Wirtz, F. Ducastelle, A. Loiseau, and J. Barjon, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 131, 206902 (2023)
<https://journals.aps.org/prl/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevLett.131.206902>
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2305.17554.pdf>

19 Seebeck Coefficient of Liquid Water from Equilibrium Molecular Dynamics, E. Drigo and S. Baroni *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 2023, 19, 23, 8855–8860 (2023)
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8.4. Annex 4: List of third party events attended by MaX consortium members

☆ invited

#	Events attended in 2024	Date	Venue	Participant(s)	
1	QUANTUM ESPRESSO on GPUs: Porting Strategy and Results (event link)	25/01/2024	online	Fabrizio Ferrari Ruffino (CNR IOM)	☆
2	A tu per tu con la scienza (event link)	5-9/02/2024	Modena	Alice Ruini (UNIMORE)	
				Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	
3	2024 APS March Meeting (event link)	4-8/03/2024	Minneapolis & online	Tommaso Gorni (CINECA)	☆
				Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	
4	CoEs first project review	22/02/2024	Luxembourg (at the EuroHPC JU premises)	All Ma1 WP Leaders	
5	Euro HPC Summit Week 2024 (event link)	18-21/03/2024	Antwerp (BE) - hybrid	Elisa Molinari (CNR) invited	☆
				Jan Jona Javorsec (IJS)	
				Andrea Ferretti (CNR-Nano)	
6	CASTIEL2 Communication workshop (event link)	22/03/2024	Brussels (BE)	Marina Corradini(ICN2)	
				Luisa Neri (CNR-Nano)	
7	Seminar at Department of Chemistry, Biology and Biotechnology - University of Perugia	18/04/2024	Perugia (Italy)	Daniele Varsano (CNR-Nano)	☆
8	CASTIEL2, EuroCC2 and CoE All-Hands Meeting (AHM)	22-24/04/2024	Tatra mountains, Slovakia	Luisa Neri (CNR-Nano)	
9	Kick-off HANAMI project	23/04/2024	Paris (FR)	Daniele Varsano (CNR-Nano)	
10	S3 SEMINAR - Nano Colloquia 2024 (event link)	09/05/2024	Modena (IT) and online	Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	☆

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11	ISC High Performance 2024 (event link)	12-16/05/2024	Hamburg (DE)	Andreas Herten (fz-juelich)	
				Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	
12	HPCSE 2024 (event link)	20–23/05/2024	Ostrava (Czech Republic)	Lubomir Riha (IT4I)	
13	Professional Careers for Scientists beyond Academia	22/05/2024	Barcelona (ES)	Marina Corradini (ICN2)	☆
14	The Future of Scientific Computing: a global perspective (event link)	27/05/2024	Trieste (IT) @ ICTP	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	
				Stefano Baroni (SISSA)	☆
				Fabio Affinito (CINECA)	
				Nicola Marzari (UBremen)	
15	MPI and OpenMP in scientific software development, course @SURF (in collaboration with NCC Netherlands, NCC founded course, within EuroCC2)	01/05/2024	Online	Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	☆
16	27th Workshop on Electronic Excitations: "Shining light on matter through interdisciplinary theoretical approaches"	3-7/06/2024	Marseille (FR)	Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	
17	27th ETSF workshop on electronic excitations	04/06/2024	Ai1-Marseille University (FR)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	
18	Career Paths Beyond the PhD (event link)	06/06/2024	Barcelona (ES)	Marina Corradini (ICN2) invited	☆
19	Austrian-Slovenian HPC Meeting 2024 – ASHPC24 (event link)	10-14/06/2024	Eugenia-Schwarzwald-Saal (Seeblickhotel Grundlsee, Austria)	Alja Prah (IJS)	
				Jan Jona Javorsek (IJS)	
20	School on Electron-Phonon Physics from First Principles (event link)	10-16/06/2024	Austin, Texas	Paolo Giannozzi (CNR)	

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21	International workshop: Physics and electronics of 2D doped materials (event link)	11-13/06/2024	Tateshina, Nagano (Japan)	Daniele Varsano (CNR-Nano)	☆
22	S3- FIM SEMINAR (event link)	11/06/2024	Modena (IT)	Pablo Ordejon (ICN2)	☆
23	Energy Efficient Computing webinar series	14/06/2024	online	Ondrej Vysocky (IT4I)	☆
24	We Make Future 2024 (event link)	15/06/2024	Bologna (IT)	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	☆
25	Lectures of First-Principles Simulations of Materials: Fundamentals and Applications to Nano-Electronics, Thermal Transport and Electrochemistry	17/06-04/07/2024	Modena (IT)	Pablo Ordejon (ICN2)	☆
26	R2B - Research to business (event link)	26-27/06/2024	Bologna (IT)	Alice Ruini (UNIMORE)	
27	AI4AM2024: Artificial Intelligence for Advanced Materials 2024 (event link)	2-4/07/2024	Barcelona (ES)	Pablo Ordejon (ICN2), co-chair	
				Elisa Molinari (CNR), International Scientific Committee	
				Nicola Marzari (UBremen)	☆
				Cristiano Malica (Bremen)	
				Michael Hernandez Bertran (UNIMORE)	
28	Frontiers in many-body excited-state dynamics from first principles (CECAM workshop)	17/07/2024	EPFL Lausanne (CH)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	☆
29	ICPS 2024	30/07/2024	Ottawa (CA)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	
30	Swiss Battery Days 2024 (event link)	26-28 /08/2024	ETH Zurich	Cristiano Malica (UBremen)	
31	EURO-PAR (event link)	26-30/08/2024	Madrid (ES)	Elisabetta Boella (E4)	

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32	1st Workshop in High-Performance Computing in Physics (PHYSHPC) (event link)	27/08/2024	Madrid (ES)	Andrea Marini (CNR)	
33	3rd Nanotech-Eurasia (hybrid) Conference on Nanotechnology and Nanomaterials (Nanotech-Eurasia) (event link)	5-7/09/2024	(hybrid) Istanbul, Turkey	Julio Gutierrez (BSC)	☆
34	SIF - Congresso Nazionale Società Italiana di Fisica	09-13/09/2024	Bologna (IT)	Fabrizio Ferrari Ruffino (SISSA)	
				Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA)	☆
				Andrea MARINI	
				Vinicius Alves Bastos (CNR- Nano)	☆
				Matteo D'Alessio (CNR- Nano)	☆
				Giacomo Sesti (CNR- Nano)	
				Antimo Marrazzo (SISSA)	
				Pino D'Amico (CNR- Nano)	☆
35	eMRS 2024 Fall Meeting	18/09/2024	Warsaw University of Technology (PL)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR- Nano)	☆
36	Webinar sui Nuovi Materiali	23/09/2024	Online	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	
37	ETSF Electron-Phonon collaboration team meeting	24/09/2024	UCL Louvain-la-neuve (BE)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR- Nano)	☆
38	11th International Conference on Multiscale Materials Modeling (MMM-11) (event link)	22-27/09/2024	Prague (CZ)	Pablo Ordejon (IT4I)	
39		23-27/09/2024	Wien (AT)	Marco Gibertini (UNIMORE)	

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	Spin-Orbit Entangled Quantum Magnetism (event link)			Stefan Blügel (fz-juelich)	
40	European Researchers Night (event link)	27/09/2024	Modena (IT)	Claudia Cardoso, Giacomo Sesti, and Matteo D'Alessio (CNR-Nano)	
41	European Researchers Night (event link)	27/09/2024	Trieste (IT)	Antimo Marrazzo (SISSA)	
42	GDR-HOWDI Low-dimensional Van der Waals heterostructures	01/10/2024	Luxembourg (LU)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	☆
43	NVIDIA Developers Summit on Atomistic Simulation	1-3/10/2024	Bologna (IT)	Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	☆
				Nicola Marzari (UBremen)	☆
				Ivan Carnimeo and Pietro Delugas (SISSA)	☆
44	EUPE1 Forum	10/10/2024	Barcelona (ES)	Erwan Raffin (Eviden)	
45	second EuroHPC User Day	22-23/10/2024	Amsterdam (NL)	Elisa Molinari (CNR) and Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA)	
46	Ma1 Meeting in Bremen	24-25/10/2024	Bremen (DE)	Representatives of all Ma1 partners	
47	CASTIEL2: 2nd NCCs-CoEs online meeting	08/11/2024	online	CASTIEL2, NCCs, CoEs	
48	SC24 - Supercomputing Conference	17-22/11/2024	Atlanta (US)	Lubomir Riha and Ondrej Vysocky (IT4I)	
49	SIGDIUS seminar- University of Stuttgart (DE)	04/12/2024	Online	Andrea Ferretti (CNR-Nano)	☆
50	Days of the Slovenian supercomputer network	3-5/12/2024	Ljubljana (SI)	Anton Kokalj and Jan Jona Javorsek (IJS)	
51	Castiel2 "Code of the month" series with Siesta	11/12/2024	online	Pablo Ordejon (ICN2)	☆

#	Events attended in 2023	Date	Venue	Participant(s)	
1	21st International Workshop on Computational Physics	11-13/01/2023	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Andrea Ferretti (CNR-Nano)	☆

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	and Materials Science: Total Energy and Force Methods (event link)			Stefano Baroni (SISSA)	☆
				Emilio Artacho (ICN2)	☆
				Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	
2	From the Materials 2030 Manifesto towards a Strategic Agenda for advanced materials (event link)	11/01/2023	online	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	☆
3	CASTIEL2 Kick-off meeting	8-9/02/2023	HLRS Stuttgart (DE)	Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	
4	From women's eyes (event link)	10/02/2023	online	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	☆
5	Ma1 Kick-off meeting	20-21-22/02/2023	Modena (IT)	Ma1 Consortium	
6	Quantum ESPRESSO Targeting Accelerators	27-28/02/2023	ICTP Trieste (IT)	SISSA, CINECA, and CNR groups	
7	S3 SEMINAR - Nano Colloquia 2023: Fulvio Paleari	02/03/2023	CNR Modena (IT)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	☆
8	APS March Meeting 2023	5-10/03/2023	Las Vegas	Pablo Ordejon (ICN2)	☆
9	Euro HPC Summit Week 2023 (event link)	20-23/03/2023	Gotheborg (SE)	Elisa Molinari, Andrea Ferretti, and Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	
				Daniele Gregori(E4)	
				Daniele Cesarini (CINECA)	
				Alja Prah, Barbara Krašovec, and Jan Jona Javoršek (IJS)	
				Estela Suarez (fz-julich)	
10	DPG Spring Meeting of the Condensed Matter Section (SKM)	26-31/03/2023	Technical University Dresden	Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	

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11	Efficient many-body perturbation theory calculations in 2D materials via the interpolation of the screened interaction: GW corrections and EELS spectra (event link)	28/04/2023	online	Alberto Guandalini (CNR-Nano)	
12	JUBE	09/05/2023	online	Laura Bellentani (CINECA)	
13	ETSF informal meeting (ETSF event)	16/05/2023	Amsterdam (NL)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	
14	Workshop on Frontiers in E1cited State Electronic Structure Methods: from Spectroscopy to Photochemistry (event link)	16-19/05/2023	Trieste (IT) @ ICTP	Daniele Varsano (CNR-Nano)	☆
				Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA)	☆
15	ISC High Performance 2023 (event link)	21-25/05/2023	Hamburg (DE)	Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	
				Daniele Gregori (E4)	
				Alja Prah (IJS)	
16	Exciton transport in 2D materials	02/06/2023	Donostia/San Sebastian (ES)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	☆
17	ICONTA 2023 " International Conference on Nanostructures: from Theory to Applications" (event link)	7-8/06/2023	Kenitra (Morocco)	Amine Slassi (CNR-Nano)	
18	Research to Business R2B (event link)	8-9/06/2023	Bologna (IT)	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	☆
19	MPI and OpenMP in Scientific Software Development (event link) collaboration with NCC Netherlands, NCC founded course (within EuroCC2)	12-14/06/2023	online	Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	
20	7th African School on Electronic Structure Methods and Application (event link)	12-23/06/2023	Kigali Rwanda	Andrea Marini (CNR ISM)	

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21	Austrian-Slovenian HPC Meeting 2023 (event link)	13-15/06/2023	Maribor (Slovenia)	Alja Prah (IJS)	☆
				Barbara Krašovec (IJS)	
				Jan Jona Javoršek (IJS)	
22	The 1st African Summer School on Molecular Modelling (event link)	13-16/06/2023	Kenitra (Morocco)	Amine Slassi (CNR-Nano)	
23	LUMI GPU Hackathon	04-06/09/2023	Finland	Laura Bellentani (CINECA)	
				Oscar Baseggio (SISSA)	
				Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA)	
24	How E1citing! 2023 workshop (event link)	2-7/8/2023	Berlin (Germany)	Julio Gutiérrez (BSC)	☆
25	CMD30 FisMat joint conference	4-8/09/2023	Politecnico di Milano and the Università degli Studi di Milano (IT)	Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	
26	CMD30/FisMat 2023 joint conference	06/09/2023	Milano (IT)	Fulvio Paleari (CNR-Nano)	
27	Solar2Chem Conference (event link)	18-22/9/2023	Tarragona (Spain)	Julio Gutiérrez (BSC)	☆
28	European Researchers Night	29/09/2023	Modena (IT)	Claudia Cardoso (CNR-Nano)	☆
29	Towards exascale solutions in Green function methods and advanced DFT (event link)	07/10/2023	Paphos (Cyprus)	Isidre Mas (BSC)	☆
30	Cross-cutting workshop, 10th Anniversary of EIG-Concert Japan programme	17/10/2023	Warwaw (Poland)	Julio Gutiérrez (BSC)	☆
31	Ma1 Internal Meeting (event link)	16-17/10/2023	Barcelona (ES)	Ma1 Consortium	

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32	Workshop to update of the PRACE Scientific and Innovation Case for Computing in Europe	20/10/2023	Paris (FR)	Elisa Molinari (CNR)	☆
33	Introduction to Leonardo HPC cluster, for users and developers (event link)	27/10/2023	Bologna @ CINECA (IT)	Laura Bellentani (CINECA) Nicola Spallanzani (CNR-Nano)	
34	SC23 - Supercomputing Conference (event link)	12-17/11/2023	Denver (US)	Andreas Herten (fz-jülich) Lubomir Riha, Ondrej Vysocky, & Marketa Dobiasova (IT4I)	
35	Slovenian supercomputer network day (event link)	16/11/2023	Slovenia	Anton Kokalj (IJS)	☆
36	Hackathon LUMI	27/11-01/12/2023	Cracovia (PL)	Lubomir Riha (IT4I) Andrea Ferretti & Nicola Spallanzani (CNR)	
37	OpenMP Users Monthly Teleconferences (event link)	01/12/2023	online	Laura Bellentani (CINECA) & Fabrizio Ferrari Ruffino (CNR-IOM) invited	☆
38	1 Workshop on Novel Methods for Electronic Structure Calculations (event link)	4-6/12/2023	La Plata, Argentina	Paolo Giannozzi (CNR-IOM)	☆
39	Best Practices for CernVM-FS for HPC (event link)	04/12/2023	online	Barbara Krašovec (IJS)	
40	Streaming Optimised Scientific Software: an Introduction to EESSI (event link)	05/12/2023	online	Barbara Krašovec (IJS)	
41	International Conference on Emerging phenomena in quantum materials	11-15/12/2023	online	Daniele Varsano (CNR)	☆
42	Euro HPC User Day (event link)	11/12/2023	Brussels (BE)	Elisa Molinari (CNR) Ivan Carnimeo (SISSA) Barbara Krašovec (IJS)	☆ ☆